

SolarNIMBY

Perceptions and willingness to accept large solar farms in rural areas

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Final Report
2026

Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade de Lisboa

Projeto financiado por:

oObservatórioSocial

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DESENVOLVIMENTO
DE CIÊNCIAS

Project funded under the FP23-2B / “The social impact of Climate Change in Portugal” call issued by the Social Observatory of ‘la Caixa’ Foundation, project # LCF/PR/FP23/62020029.

Suggested citation:

Fernando Ascensão, João Mourato, Ana Horta, Sergio Chozas, Helena Serrano, and Cristina Branquinho. 2026. *Solar NIMBY in Portugal: Social Acceptance of Large-Scale Photovoltaic Farms in Rural Communities*. Lisbon: University of Lisbon / SolarNIMBY Project.

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Executive summary

Portugal is rapidly expanding utility scale photovoltaic farms to meet national and European Union climate targets. Drawing on a systematic literature review and a field survey of 610 residents across eleven major regions, this study examined the social acceptance of large solar energy projects in rural Portugal. Respondents were predominantly long-term residents, with more than three quarters having lived in their area for over thirty years, which demonstrates strong place attachment and extensive local knowledge.

Our findings reveal a paradox of acceptance. Although there was widespread criticism of planning processes, particularly regarding the lack of opportunities for participation, limited possibilities to voice concerns, and insufficient involvement of municipal authorities, almost half of respondents indicated that they would authorize the construction of a solar park near their area of residence. About forty percent expressed opposition and around fifteen percent were undecided. This suggests that acceptance is not a matter of simple support or rejection but rather a form of conditional approval in which substantive support for renewable energy coexists with dissatisfaction about governance and procedural practices.

Our analysis highlights four themes that structure community responses: i) A participatory paradox, whereby communities express strong criticism of procedures but remain open to project outcomes when these align with local priorities. ii) Economic development emerges as a highly salient consideration, but it coexists with strong environmental concern and governance-related expectations. iii) The politics of scale, since support declines as project size increases while smaller scale or integrated solutions such as agrivoltaics enjoy higher levels of acceptance. iv) Rural agency, as communities demonstrate informed and critical evaluation frameworks that cannot be dismissed under simplistic notions of opposition.

Trust also emerges as a decisive factor. Academic researchers and civil protection agencies are regarded as the most credible sources of information, while energy companies and national level political actors are viewed with scepticism. Looking ahead, residents expressed clear preferences for process improvements. These include limiting the scale of projects, strengthening opportunities for public participation, improving communication and transparency, and promoting land use integrated approaches such as agrivoltaics.

We conclude that Portugal enjoys a unique window of opportunity. Rural communities remain open to renewable energy development, but their support is conditional on more meaningful governance arrangements. Addressing issues of procedural justice and embedding

local participation into planning processes will be essential to prevent conditional acceptance from turning into entrenched opposition. By acting at this stage, Portugal can sustain its momentum in renewable energy while ensuring that rural communities are partners rather than adversaries in the energy transition.

Introduction

We stand at a critical historical moment, as it is vital to swiftly transition to renewable energy sources in order to limit greenhouse gas emissions and reduce dependency on oil and gas exporting nations (Clarke et al., 2022). The European Union has set ambitious targets under the REPowerEU initiative to spearhead this transition, with a strong emphasis on accelerating permit processes for renewable energy projects (EC, 2022). The designation of Renewable Energy Acceleration Areas reflects a concentrated effort to facilitate this expansion. The European Commission's proposal of September 2020 (55% emission reduction by 2030 compared to 1990 levels) and the subsequent European Parliament proposal (60% reduction) have substantially raised the level of ambition. Achieving these goals will require an unprecedented deployment of renewable energy capacity (Kougias et al., 2021).

In Portugal, the government aims for renewable sources to account for 51% of gross final energy consumption by 2030 (PNEC 2030, 2024), with a significant share expected to come from utility-scale photovoltaic facilities (hereafter "PV parks"). This target is driving a rapid expansion of PV parks across the country, particularly in rural areas. However, this process is not without challenges, especially concerning potential land use conflicts. PV parks require far larger areas of land than fossil fuel plants (Palmer-Wilson et al., 2019), and suitable sites must also meet a series of technical constraints such as the proximity to the distribution grid. These factors increase the likelihood of competition with other land uses, including agriculture and biodiversity conservation (Gove et al., 2016; Katkar et al., 2021).

This occupation, competition over land use and structural shifts in local landscapes may trigger or intensify social conflicts directed at both energy companies and government authorities, as rural populations may oppose the installation of PV parks in close proximity to their communities. In recent years, there has been a global noticeable increase in publicly reported cases, widely covered by the media, of local communities expressing resistance to the installation of PV systems near their homes (Brás et al., 2024; O'Neil, 2021; Susskind et al., 2022). This resistance is likely driven by concerns over potential negative impacts on local livelihoods, the natural environment and landscape, and traditional practices. At its core, it echoes the NIMBY phenomena ("Not In My Backyard") (Foster and Warren, 2022).

NIMBYism may stem from a range of factors, including value-based objections (that is, concerns not rooted in financial gains or losses but in cultural, environmental, or place-based values); institutional and procedural complexities that exacerbate tensions between project proponents and local opponents; and, most notably, the lack of community engagement in the planning and management of areas designated for PV development, particularly when local residents do not perceive any tangible benefits from it (Bessette et al., 2024; Campos et al., 2023; Foster and Warren, 2022; Susskind et al., 2022). However, to the best of our knowledge, few studies have directly engaged rural communities to assess their acceptance of large-scale PV installations near their home places, particularly through a systematic inquiry that captures the diversity of local perspectives, concerns, and expectations regarding these developments.

Why this research?

The social and environmental significance of this research is underscored by the need to balance energy production with rural landscapes, biodiversity, and community well-being (Hilker et al., 2024). A major challenge posed by the expansion of PV parks is their competition with agricultural land use and conservation areas. This conflict reflects broader societal tensions between short-term economic imperatives and long-term goals of food security and environmental sustainability. Another major challenge is the perceived degradation of rural landscapes, which for many communities embodies cultural identity, heritage, and a sense of place. The visual and spatial transformation brought about by large-scale PV parks can therefore provoke strong symbolic and emotional opposition.

Against this background, this research aims to understand societal attitudes towards large solar farms among rural communities. It explores the complexities of PV parks' acceptance, considering the balance between economic needs, environmental sustainability, and cultural heritage. By examining these dynamics, this study seeks to inform more inclusive and context-sensitive territorialized policy approaches for renewable energy deployment in the face of climate change. In other words, this study focuses on informing a socially just and resilient energy transition.

Changes from the original project proposal

The original research proposal suffered a few adjustments related to practical and methodological constraints. Urban areas were not included in the field survey, as we underestimated the effort required to conduct simultaneous surveys in both rural and urban contexts, which would have required distinct sampling strategies, data collection tools, and analytical frameworks. These challenges were further compounded by the limited timeframe available for fieldwork and delays encountered at the project's outset. We opted to concentrate our efforts on rural areas, where data on public perceptions of solar farm installations remains scarce. This decision was strengthened by the acknowledgment that rural territories are at the forefront of solar energy expansion in Portugal, and yet little empirical data exists on how local communities perceive and experience these developments. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study, in Portugal, to gather data on this topic with such a geographical scope and depth.

We also decided not to include locations where PV parks are still at the planning stage. Our concern was that residents in those areas may not have formed clear or strong opinions about these projects that have not yet materialized in their immediate surroundings. Instead, we focused on communities where PV parks are already operational, under construction, or in advanced stages of permitting — specifically, those with granted construction licenses. This approach ensured that respondents had a more concrete underpinning of their views and experiences.

Structure of the Report

This report is structured into several sections to provide a logical and comprehensive analysis of the study. Following the Introduction, which outlines the background, objectives, and relevance of the research, we present a State-of-the-Art review that synthesizes existing literature on social perceptions and acceptance of large solar farms in rural areas. The Methodology section then details the procedures followed for field data collection protocols, including the selection of sites, the structure of the questionnaire, and the analytical strategies employed. The Results section presents the main findings of the survey, organized according to the major themes addressed in the questionnaire. These findings are then interpreted in the Discussion, where they are compared with insights from the literature review and implications for policy and practice are highlighted. Finally, the report Conclusions summarize the main contributions of the study and suggest

directions for future research and policy development. Supplementary materials, such as the full questionnaire and a list of reviewed studies, are provided in the Annexes.

State-of-the art on perceptions and willingness to accept large solar farms in rural areas

Research on perceptions and willingness to accept large solar farms in rural areas has emerged globally as a critical area of inquiry due to the increasing deployment of renewable energy technologies and their significant landscape and social impacts (e.g., Campos et al., 2023; Carlisle et al., 2015; Ko, 2023; Sato and Ngoc, 2024). Despite broad public support for renewable energy, including solar, the rapid growth of large-scale PV parks in rural landscapes has raised concerns about environmental, economic, and social consequences (Cousse, 2021). For instance, surveys indicate that while general acceptance of solar energy is high, acceptance decreases with the scale of installations, highlighting the importance of understanding local community perspectives (Campos et al., 2023; Cousse, 2021). The specific problem addressed is the frequent local opposition and varied perceptions toward large PV parks in rural settings, despite overall societal support for renewable energy (Nilson and Stedman, 2023, 2022).

The literature reveals a knowledge gap concerning the nuanced factors influencing acceptance, including procedural justice, distributive fairness, landscape integration, and socio-cultural values (Hazrati, 2024; Ko, 2023). While some studies emphasize economic benefits and job creation as drivers of acceptance (Trandafir et al., 2023; Zander et al., 2024), others highlight concerns about environmental degradation, visual impacts, and perceived urban bias (Ko, 2023). Controversies also arise regarding the extent to which local communities are involved in decision-making and benefit-sharing, with procedural injustices often fuelling resistance (Stadelmann-Steffen and Dermont, 2021; Tsoeu-Ntokoane et al., 2024). The consequences of this gap include delays in project implementation and challenges to achieving renewable energy targets (Hazrati, 2024; Ko, 2023).

To ensure a comprehensive and focused review of existing literature on the topic of "Perceptions and willingness to accept large solar farms in rural areas," we began by systematically refining the original research question into multiple, more specific search queries. This approach allowed us to target distinct facets of the broader topic while minimizing the risk of overlooking

niche or terminology-specific studies. The key search statements included: 1) *perceptions and willingness to accept large solar farms in rural areas*, 2) *how community engagement influences social acceptance of large-scale solar farms in rural areas*, and 3) *what community factors and engagement strategies enhance social acceptance of large-scale solar energy projects in rural regions*.

To review this body of work, we conducted a systematic literature search using the AI-assisted research platform SciSpace (<https://scispace.com/>), where each of these refined queries was executed against a research database containing over 270 million academic papers. In addition to direct database searches, we employed citation chaining to identify further relevant studies. Backward citation chaining involved examining the reference lists of core papers to capture foundational works, while forward citation chaining identified newer studies citing these core papers, thereby revealing recent developments and ongoing debates. An initial pool of 131 candidate papers, we were able to add through the citation chaining process an additional 113 relevant papers. The combined pool of 244 papers was then subjected to a relevance scoring and sorting process. This step prioritized studies most closely aligned with our research objective. This final pool of papers was then analysed in more detail (by researchers), after which we selected 30 studies as highly pertinent to the central research question after reading the abstract and its content (list of studies in the Annex 4).

This systematic review aimed to synthesize empirical insights into rural perceptions and the willingness to accept large solar farms, identifying key drivers and barriers to acceptance as discussed in global studies. These findings were used to discuss our results, within the Discussion section.

Main thematic lines found in the systematic review

The deployment of utility-scale solar photovoltaic installations in rural landscapes has generated substantial academic interest in understanding the factors that influence community acceptance and opposition. The literature demonstrates that social acceptance of solar farms extends far beyond simple economic calculations or environmental concerns. Instead, acceptance emerges from the dynamic interplay of participatory processes, justice perceptions, trust relationships, landscape considerations, and cultural contexts. These findings challenge reductive explanations and highlight the need for nuanced, context-sensitive approaches to understanding and facilitating

rural renewable energy transitions. In the following sections we address the eight main thematic lines covered within the 30 most relevant studies assessed.

Theme 1: Community engagement and participation

Community involvement emerges as the most prominent theme in the literature, establishing participatory processes as fundamental to solar farm acceptance. The research consistently demonstrates that transparent information sharing and meaningful participation in decision-making are crucial to fostering acceptance of large-scale solar projects in rural areas (Bessette et al., 2024; Nilson and Stedman, 2023; Sato and Ngoc, 2024). Studies emphasize the positive impact of local ownership models, which prioritize community involvement and benefit in projects, and provide communities with direct financial stakes and greater control over development processes (Tsoeu-Ntokoane et al., 2024). In-person engagement emerges as particularly effective compared to remote consultation methods, suggesting that face-to-face relationship building remains essential in rural contexts. The literature also highlights the valuable role of third-party intermediaries in building trust and establishing social license, particularly in situations where initial relationships between developers and communities are strained (Stadelmann-Steffen and Dermont, 2021). Conversely, the absence of meaningful participation consistently leads to opposition and perceptions of procedural injustice. Communities that feel excluded from decision-making processes often develop lasting negative attitudes toward projects, even when those projects might otherwise provide significant benefits. These findings underscore that participatory processes are not merely consultative exercises but fundamental requirements for establishing the social license necessary for successful solar development.

Theme 2: Economic and environmental factors influencing acceptance

Economic and environmental considerations form the second most prevalent theme, revealing that rural communities engage in complex assessments that weigh multiple types of impacts simultaneously. Economic benefits such as job creation, local income opportunities, and cost savings significantly drive acceptance, though the literature suggests that communities distinguish between different types and qualities of economic benefits (Bessette et al., 2024; Sato and Ngoc, 2024; Trandafir et al., 2023). The research indicates that long-term employment opportunities are valued more highly than temporary construction jobs, and that local procurement policies and hiring requirements can significantly enhance the perceived economic value of projects (Hilker et

al., 2024; Torma and Aschemann-Witzel, 2023). Environmental considerations present a more nuanced picture, with communities generally recognizing renewable energy's role in addressing climate goals while expressing concerns about local environmental impacts including effects on biodiversity and landscape quality. The literature reveals that acceptance depends heavily on how communities weigh global climate benefits against local environmental costs, with effective environmental impact assessments and mitigation measures playing crucial roles in addressing these concerns. Land use competition emerges as a particularly significant issue, especially in agriculturally productive areas where communities worry about permanent conversion of farmland and implications for local food security and agricultural identity (see following theme).

Theme 3: Perceptions and Acceptance of Agrivoltaic Systems

Agrivoltaics, which integrate agricultural production with solar energy generation, are increasingly recognized as a promising approach to mitigate land-use conflicts and enhance local acceptance of renewable energy projects (Gorjian et al., 2022; Pascaris et al., 2022, 2021). By maintaining agricultural functionality while producing clean energy, agrivoltaic systems generally receive more favourable public evaluations than conventional solar farms (Biró-Varga et al., 2024; Torma and Aschemann-Witzel, 2023). Farmer willingness to adopt these systems is shaped by perceived usefulness for crop production, opportunities for income diversification, supportive regulatory frameworks, and prevailing social norms (Cuppari et al., 2024; Wagner et al., 2024). Multi-stakeholder studies further suggest that regional conditions and crop protection benefits can strengthen acceptance. Nonetheless, significant challenges remain. Visual impact concerns persist, particularly regarding the industrial appearance of solar infrastructure in traditional agricultural landscapes (Moore et al., 2022; Sirnik et al., 2024). Uncertainties also remain about long-term effects on soil health, crop yields, and local ecosystems, highlighting the need for sustained monitoring and adaptive system design. Moreover, empirical research on the social acceptance of agrivoltaics is still limited and geographically concentrated, constraining the generalizability of current findings (Cuppari et al., 2024). Barriers such as regulatory uncertainty, questions of economic viability, and integration challenges with existing farming practices (Wagner et al., 2024) continue to hinder wider adoption. Overall, while agrivoltaics offer a compelling pathway to align energy and agricultural priorities, their success will depend on addressing these technical, environmental, and institutional challenges alongside broader stakeholder engagement.

Theme 4: Landscape change and visual impact

Landscape alteration and aesthetic concerns constitute the fourth most significant theme, highlighting the importance of visual and cultural considerations in rural solar development. The literature reveals that opposition often stems not from fundamental objection to renewable energy, but from concerns about changes to valued rural landscapes and their associated cultural meanings (Carlisle et al., 2015; Cousse, 2021; O'Neil, 2021; Zander et al., 2024). Visual impact assessments emerge as important tools for understanding and mitigating landscape concerns, with research indicating community preferences for low-profile installations, earth-toned or coloured panels, and design adaptations that follow natural topography rather than imposing geometric patterns on the landscape (Schauppenlehner et al., 2022). The literature suggests that landscape integration strategies, including screening vegetation and appropriate setbacks from roads and residences, can help reduce perceived visual harm while maintaining project viability. The research also reveals cultural dimensions to landscape concerns, with rural landscapes often carrying significant historical and identity-based meaning for local communities (Moore et al., 2022). Solar installations can be perceived as threats to place-based identity and heritage, requiring careful attention to local knowledge and cultural values in project design and siting decisions (Nilson and Stedman, 2022; Schwenkenbecher, 2017). This finding emphasizes that technical visual impact assessments must be complemented by understanding of cultural landscape values and community attachment to place.

Theme 5: Procedural and distributive justice

Perceptions of fairness in benefit distribution and decision-making processes strongly affect willingness to accept solar developments. The literature distinguishes between procedural justice, which involves fairness in decision-making processes including transparency and opportunities for local influence; and distributive justice, which concerns equitable distribution of economic benefits and environmental burdens (Ko, 2025, 2023; Nilson and Stedman, 2023). Procedural justice emerges as particularly important, with research demonstrating that communities that feel they have been treated fairly in development processes are more likely to accept projects even when material benefits are limited. Conversely, perceptions of unfair treatment can sustain opposition even when projects provide substantial economic benefits (Ko, 2025; Trandafir et al., 2023). The literature emphasizes that justice perceptions are often more influential than objective measures

of fairness, highlighting the importance of process design and community engagement approaches (Schwenkenbecher, 2017). Distributive justice concerns focus on ensuring that those who bear the visual, environmental, and social impacts of projects receive commensurate benefits (Vuichard et al., 2021). The research suggests that benefit-sharing mechanisms must be designed with attention to local preferences and values rather than imposed through external frameworks, and that effective distributive justice requires ongoing attention throughout project development and operation phases (Hazrati, 2024).

Theme 6: Regional and cultural variations in acceptance

Acceptance patterns vary significantly across regions and cultures. The literature reveals that acceptance is influenced by socio-demographic factors, local identities, and historical experiences with resource development, underscoring the need for context-sensitive approaches to solar development (Carlisle et al., 2015; Ko, 2025, 2023; Scovell et al., 2024; Zander et al., 2024). Rural communities may express distinct concerns related to traditional land uses and cultural preservation, requiring patient and respectful engagement approaches that accommodate different decision-making processes and timelines (Campos et al., 2023; Cousse, 2021; Nilson and Stedman, 2022). Historical experiences with extractive industries can significantly influence attitudes toward new energy developments, with some communities expressing scepticism based on past experiences of exploitation or unfulfilled promises (Zander et al., 2024). Regional economic conditions also shape acceptance patterns, with the literature suggesting that areas with limited economic opportunities may be more receptive to solar development due to prospects for economic benefits, while more prosperous regions may prioritize landscape preservation over economic gains (Hanger et al., 2016). Understanding these regional and cultural contexts is essential for developing appropriate engagement strategies and benefit-sharing mechanisms that resonate with local values and priorities.

Theme 7: Role of trust and knowledge in solar farm acceptance

Trust in developers and perceived knowledge levels about solar projects emerge as significant factors correlating with support. The research reveals complex relationships between information provision, trust building, and attitude formation (Hanger et al., 2016; Sato and Ngoc, 2024; Scovell et al., 2024). This finding suggests that information provision strategies must be carefully designed to provide credible, comprehensive, and accessible information while avoiding information

overload or manipulation. Educational efforts and credible communication consistently improve attitudes toward solar projects, but the research emphasizes that trust-building requires sustained commitment to transparent communication, consistent behaviour over time, and demonstration of genuine concern for community welfare. Third-party endorsements from trusted local institutions can help establish credibility, particularly in contexts where developers are viewed with initial suspicion or scepticism.

Theme 8: Policy and community benefit mechanisms

Legally binding contracts between developers and community groups that ensure development projects provide tangible benefits to the local area (Community Benefit Agreements), and participatory policies that ensure local economic and social gains emerge as effective strategies for increasing acceptance. The literature suggests that well-designed benefit mechanisms can help address distributive justice concerns while providing tangible demonstration of developer commitment to community welfare (Hazrati, 2024; Trandafir et al., 2023). Research indicates that community preferences lean toward voluntary, private benefit distributions that align with local values and priorities rather than mandatory tax-based mechanisms or externally imposed benefit packages. Effective benefit agreements may include direct payments, community infrastructure investments, educational programs, environmental enhancements, or support for local economic development initiatives. The literature emphasizes that successful benefit mechanisms require genuine consultation with affected communities to identify priorities and preferences, rather than developer-driven approaches that may not resonate with local needs (Stadelmann-Steffen and Dermont, 2021). Policy frameworks that require meaningful community engagement and benefit-sharing can help establish minimum standards for social acceptability while maintaining flexibility to accommodate diverse local contexts and preferences.

Evidence from Portugal

Several studies have examined public perceptions of renewable energy in Portugal, offering valuable insights into the acceptance of large-scale solar projects. Ribeiro et al. (2014) conducted a national survey involving 3,646 respondents to assess public opinion toward four renewable technologies—hydro, wind, biomass, and solar. Solar energy emerged as the most favourably perceived, with respondents citing its environmental and economic benefits. While overall support for renewables was strong, NIMBY attitudes were limited and most pronounced in municipalities

hosting biomass facilities. Solar, by contrast, encountered minimal local resistance. Interestingly, willingness to pay for renewables was higher among those who believed such technologies would raise electricity costs, though this belief was not widely held.

Delicado et al. (2016) adopted a qualitative approach through case studies of three wind farms and one solar plant in Amareleja—the only large-scale solar facility (over 15 MW) in the country at the time. Using approximately 25 public-space interviews per site, the study revealed heterogeneous local perceptions concerning environmental, visual, and socioeconomic impacts. The authors emphasized the importance of monitoring public attitudes not only during project planning and implementation but also post-deployment, as perceptions may evolve. The findings highlight the necessity of integrating both the positive and negative dimensions of renewable energy development to enhance social acceptance.

More recently, Campos et al. (Campos et al., 2023) investigated societal acceptance and energy citizenship in Portugal and Spain through around 400 interviews in each country. Their results suggest that large-scale solar PV projects are generally well accepted, with media-driven protests reflecting minority dissent rather than widespread opposition. Citizen participation was found to significantly enhance satisfaction with projects, although preferences leaned toward small to medium-scale systems that allow more direct involvement. High levels of environmental awareness and concern for biodiversity contributed to acceptance, especially for projects that benefit vulnerable groups—indicating strong public support for principles of energy justice and social inclusion. Nonetheless, information asymmetries, particularly regarding decentralized technologies such as energy communities, constrained broader engagement. The study calls for greater transparency, improved energy literacy, and active municipal involvement to ensure equitable and participatory energy transitions.

Synthesis of literature review

The collective body of literature on perceptions and willingness to accept large solar farms in rural areas reveals a complex interplay of social, environmental, economic, and cultural factors shaping acceptance dynamics. Local residents demonstrate a generally positive attitude towards solar energy projects, especially when these developments are accompanied by transparent, comprehensive information disclosure and meaningful community engagement. Active participation and procedural justice emerge as critical components fostering trust and social

license, mitigating opposition rooted in perceptions of unfair burden-sharing or exclusion from decision-making. Nevertheless, opposition often arises from concerns about landscape change, visual impacts, and the perceived disruption of rural identity and environmental quality, highlighting the centrality of aesthetic and ecological considerations in rural contexts.

Economic factors play a pivotal role, with acceptance strongly linked to the distribution and visibility of tangible local benefits such as job creation, additional income for landowners, and investment opportunities. Communities express nuanced preferences for benefit-sharing mechanisms, often favouring private or voluntary agreements over mandated collective schemes. This economic dimension is further complicated by perceptions of urban bias, where rural residents feel disproportionately burdened by renewable energy development that primarily benefits urban centres, underscoring the importance of equitable and context-sensitive policy frameworks. Cultural and regional variability significantly influences acceptance patterns. Socio-demographic variables such as education and environmental values generally correlate with support, though their effects are context-dependent and intertwined with emotional responses, which have been identified as influential but remain underexplored.

An emerging and promising avenue to reconcile land-use conflicts and enhance acceptance is agrivoltaic technology, which integrates solar energy production with agricultural activities. Agrivoltaics is associated with higher social acceptance relative to conventional large-scale solar farms due to its multifunctional land use, economic benefits for farmers, and potential to reduce ecological impacts. Nonetheless, barriers such as regulatory uncertainty, economic viability challenges, and concerns over visual and operational integration temper widespread adoption. The current empirical evidence on agrivoltaics' social acceptance is still limited and concentrated in specific regions, indicating a need for broader, longitudinal research.

Regarding information from Portugal, the few studies here performed provide valuable insights that both corroborate and extend these international findings. Solar energy enjoys particularly favourable perceptions compared to other renewable technologies, with apparent minimal NIMBY resistance. Qualitative case studies, including the pioneering Amareleja solar plant, reveal heterogeneous local perceptions that emphasize the importance of monitoring attitudes throughout project lifecycles rather than only during planning phases. More recent comparative research indicates that while large-scale solar projects are generally well accepted, citizen participation significantly enhances satisfaction, with clear preferences for smaller-scale systems that enable more direct community involvement. The Portuguese context also highlights how high

environmental awareness and concern for biodiversity can facilitate acceptance, particularly for projects demonstrating benefits for vulnerable groups, though information asymmetries regarding decentralized technologies remain a constraint on broader engagement. These findings underscore the need for enhanced transparency, improved energy literacy, and active municipal involvement to ensure equitable and participatory energy transitions in Mediterranean rural contexts where agricultural landscapes and solar resources coincide.

Research gaps

Despite the valuable contributions of published literature to understanding solar farm acceptance, significant empirical gaps remain that limit our ability to fully comprehend the complex dynamics of rural energy transitions in the Iberian Peninsula. While existing Portuguese studies have provided important baseline insights through national surveys and small-scale qualitative case studies, none have undertaken large-scale, systematic investigation of rural community responses to the current wave of utility-scale photovoltaic development that is transforming the Portuguese landscape. The Ribeiro et al. (2014) national survey, though comprehensive in scope, was conducted before the major expansion of utility-scale solar facilities that has characterized the past decade. The Delicado et al. (2016) case studies, while methodologically valuable, were limited to approximately 25 interviews per site and focused on a single solar facility in a country that now hosts dozens of large-scale installations. The Campos et al. (2023) research, though more recent, was primarily comparative between Portugal and Spain rather than providing in-depth analysis of Portuguese rural contexts specifically.

Our study addresses these limitations by providing the first comprehensive, large-scale survey of rural attitudes toward utility-scale solar development in Portugal. With 610 interviews conducted across 11 solar park projects spanning multiple regions of the Portuguese interior, this research represents the most extensive empirical investigation of solar farm acceptance in rural Iberian communities to our knowledge. The study focuses specifically on the Alentejo region, an area that Portuguese national energy planning has identified as a key target for utility-scale photovoltaic development due to their exceptional solar resources, available land, and strategic positioning within European energy networks. These regions have experienced rapid solar development over the past decade, transforming rural landscapes and creating new socioeconomic dynamics that have not been systematically studied at scale. By examining actual experiences with operational and recently constructed facilities rather than hypothetical scenarios,

this research provides crucial empirical evidence for understanding how theoretical frameworks of renewable energy acceptance apply in practice within Mediterranean rural contexts facing intensive solar development pressures.

Field survey

This section describes the research design and implementation process. It outlines the selection of sites included in the study, the data collection procedures employed, and the concept and structure of the questionnaire used to capture local perceptions and attitudes. Finally, it details the data analysis methods, explaining how survey responses were processed and interpreted to address the research questions.

Selection of sites

For this study, we selected eleven sites with solar farms either already in operation or in advanced stages of construction (Fig. 1). The selection was designed to ensure diversity across project types, including both established facilities and those nearing completion. Geographically, the focus was placed on Portugal's interior, along a broad corridor bordering Spain, stretching from Alcoutim in the south to Fundão in the north. This corridor was chosen because it concentrates a significant share of Portugal's large-scale photovoltaic deployment, while also intersecting regions where rural livelihoods, agricultural activity, and landscape values are particularly prominent. Notably, the solar farm in Cercal was deliberately excluded from the selection. This exclusion was motivated by concerns about potential response bias, as extensive prior research and survey work had been conducted at this site (Brás et al., 2024; Campos et al., 2025; Wallace et al., 2025), which could have influenced local perceptions and introduced confounding effects into our data.

Figure 1 - Location of the eleven solar farms targeted in the field survey. Images portraying three of the surveyed solar farms are presented. Aerial images in the background are from Sentinel 2 satellite (from August 2025).

Data collection

The fieldwork was conducted by a team of 10 trained and experienced interviewers between March 3 and April 8, 2025. The target population for the survey consisted of individuals aged 18 and over residing in the previously identified zones. Respondents were selected using a quota sampling method, based on a matrix that combined the aforementioned variables. The quotas were defined according to data from the 2021 Census, provided by the Portuguese National Institute of Statistics (INE). Data collection was carried out using CAPI (Computer Assisted Personal Interviewing) methodology.

Questionnaire - concept and structure

The structured survey was designed as a comprehensive instrument to capture the multidimensional nature of solar farm acceptance in rural communities, moving beyond simple binary measures of support or opposition, to explore the complex interplay of factors that influence community attitudes toward large-scale renewable energy development. The questionnaire architecture was conceived to systematically examine both cognitive and affective dimensions of acceptance while capturing the temporal and spatial dynamics that shape community responses to solar infrastructure.

The conceptual framework underlying the questionnaire design drew from established theories of social acceptance of renewable energy technologies, incorporating insights from procedural and distributive justice literature, landscape impact assessment research, and community engagement scholarship. Rather than treating acceptance as a static phenomenon, the instrument was structured to examine how attitudes form and evolve through different phases of project development, from initial awareness through construction to operational experience. This longitudinal perspective was essential for understanding the participation paradox identified in the study, where communities could maintain substantive support despite experiencing procedural failures (see Results).

The survey instrument was organized into four primary conceptual blocks, each designed to explore distinct but interconnected dimensions of the solar farm acceptance phenomenon. The first conceptual block focused on foundational climate and energy attitudes, establishing respondents' baseline perspectives on climate change urgency, government policy adequacy, and the role of renewable energy transitions. This section was crucial for contextualizing subsequent

responses about specific solar installations, as it revealed the extent to which local solar park opinions were grounded in broader environmental values versus site-specific concerns.

The second major block examined perceptions and evaluations of solar park impacts across multiple scales and dimensions. This section systematically explored how respondents assessed both existing and anticipated consequences of solar development, distinguishing between economic, environmental, social, and procedural impacts. The design deliberately contrasted general solar energy opinions with specific local solar park assessments to identify proximity effects and experience-based attitude formation. Within this block, questions probed both positive impacts such as economic development and energy independence, and negative concerns including landscape alteration and ecological effects, allowing for nuanced cost-benefit reasoning rather than forcing respondents into simplistic pro- or anti-development positions.

The third conceptual block focused specifically on planning processes and democratic participation, exploring respondents' experiences with and evaluations of the decision-making procedures that governed solar park development in their communities. This section was designed to capture both procedural justice concerns related to transparency, inclusion, and fairness, as well as substantive assessments of how well planning processes served community interests. Questions examined multiple aspects of community engagement including access to information, opportunities for meaningful participation, quality of developer and government communication, and overall process transparency. The design allowed for separate evaluation of different institutional actors including private developers, local government, and central administration, recognizing that trust and legitimacy perceptions might vary across different levels of governance.

The fourth major block addressed future preferences and alternative development scenarios, exploring what communities wanted to see in improved planning processes and how they evaluated different land use options. This forward-looking section was essential for translating empirical findings into actionable policy recommendations, as it revealed community priorities for institutional innovation and procedural reform. Questions examined preferences for different renewable energy scales and technologies, alternative land uses including agrivoltaic concepts, and specific mechanisms for enhancing community benefit distribution and participation opportunities.

Throughout the questionnaire design, particular attention was paid to response format selection and question ordering to minimize bias while maximizing data quality. Likert-scale responses were used for attitudinal measures to capture gradations of opinion rather than forcing

binary choices, while ranking exercises were employed to reveal preference hierarchies among competing priorities. The questionnaire incorporated randomized response ordering for key question batteries to control for order effects, and included multiple measures of similar constructs to enhance reliability and allow for internal consistency checking.

The demographic and background characteristics section was positioned at the end of the survey to avoid priming effects while still capturing essential contextual variables including residence duration, education levels, economic status, and personal renewable energy experience. These variables were crucial for understanding how different community segments experienced and evaluated solar development, and for identifying potential sources of heterogeneity in acceptance patterns. The instrument design also incorporated open-ended questions at critical junctures to capture qualitative reasoning behind quantitative responses, particularly regarding authorization decisions and perceived benefits or harms of solar development. These qualitative elements provided essential context for interpreting statistical patterns and understanding the logic underlying community evaluations of solar projects.

Special consideration was given to ensuring that questions were accessible to rural populations with varying education levels while maintaining sufficient precision for academic analysis. Question wording was tested for clarity and comprehension, and response scales were designed to be intuitive while providing adequate discrimination between different levels of agreement or support. The questionnaire length was carefully calibrated to maintain respondent engagement while covering all essential dimensions of the research questions, resulting in an average interview duration of approximately fifteen minutes. The final questionnaire structure reflected a careful balance between theoretical comprehensiveness and practical implementation constraints, creating an instrument capable of generating robust empirical evidence about the complex dynamics of rural solar farm acceptance while remaining accessible to diverse community populations and feasible for large-scale field implementation across multiple geographic regions (questionnaire available in Annex 5).

Data analysis

Data analysis was conducted using a mixed-methods approach that combined descriptive statistics and cross-tabulations to explore patterns of social acceptance across the 610 survey responses. All percentage calculations were based on valid responses, systematically excluding "Don't know/No response" cases to ensure accurate representation of substantive opinions. Agreement

percentages combined "Agree" and "Strongly Agree" responses, while disagreement percentages combined "Disagree" and "Strongly Disagree" responses, with support and opposition measures following similar aggregation protocols. Cross-tabulation analysis was employed to examine relationships between key demographic variables (age, proximity to installations, residence duration) and acceptance outcomes, revealing significant age gradients and proximity effects that informed the participation paradox interpretation.

Our analysis primarily relies on descriptive statistics to characterize patterns of responses across the sample. As such, interpretations of relationships between variables are indicative rather than causal. While this approach allows for a comprehensive overview of perceptions, further inferential analyses would be valuable to formally test associations between variables and identify key drivers of acceptance.

Descriptive statistics

Descriptive analysis focused on identifying overall patterns within specific question domains, examining frequency distributions, central tendencies, and response hierarchies across the multiple dimensions of solar farm acceptance measured in the survey instrument. The analytical approach enabled systematic examination of both individual question responses and thematic clusters, revealing complex relationships between procedural experiences, substantive evaluations, and final authorization decisions. We provide a Statistical Appendix (hereafter SA) describing the calculus supporting claims. They are referred to as 'SA' and a number, to help readers understand which calculus supports each claim.

Multivariate analysis

To explore patterns of community perception regarding solar park projects, we employed Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) as a multivariate ordination technique. All survey responses were standardized by converting Likert-scale items to a 1–5 numeric format, where higher values indicated stronger agreement, adequacy, or support. Binary questions were coded as 5 ("Yes") and 1 ("No"), while non-informative responses ("Don't know"/no response) were treated as NA. The initial pool of variables reflected a broad conceptualization of social acceptance, including: (i) core acceptance measures (P2, P4, P19); (ii) impact perceptions (P5A–P5J); (iii) technology preferences (P7A–P7D); (iv) participation process evaluations (P10A–P10E); (v) future

impact expectations (P6A–P6I); (vi) perceived process effects (P11A–P11D); (vii) cost–benefit appraisals (P13A–P13C); and (viii) information trust (P18A–P18F).

Ordination was performed with the metaMDS function in *vegan* (Oksanen et al., 2025), using Bray–Curtis distance to capture relative differences in response profiles. Multiple solutions ($k = 1–4$) were evaluated with 100 random starts and the monoMDS engine to ensure convergence. Stress values guided dimensionality choice ($<0.1 = \text{good}$, $<0.2 = \text{fair}$). Shepard plots were used to assess monotonic fit, and per-point goodness-of-fit was examined to identify poorly represented cases. To interpret the ordination, environmental vector fitting (*envfit*) was used to correlate retained variables with NMDS axes and assess significance through 999 permutations. Group-level patterns were further assessed using PERMANOVA (*adonis2*) to test for regional differences (Upper North, North, Center, South). To complement this, PERMDISP tested the homogeneity of group dispersions (i.e., whether significant results reflected differences in group centroids versus variability in spread). Pairwise tests were applied when overall effects were significant. Distances in ordination space represent overall dissimilarity in response patterns, such that projects close together share more similar community attitudes. All analyses were conducted in R v4.4.2 (R Development Core Team, 2025).

Results

A total of 610 face-to-face interviews were conducted, with the sample distributed across the 11 areas of implementation of the solar parks, 2 gender groups (female 53.1%, male 46.9%) (SA1 in Statistical Appendix), and 4 age groups. The maximum margin of error for the sample is ± 4.0 percentage points at a 95% confidence level. Each interview had an average duration of approximately 15 minutes. The surveyed population represents a rural Portuguese community with a mean age of 54.6 years (SA2), characterized by long-term residence (75.9% living in their area for 30+ years) (SA3), moderate educational attainment (77.7% with secondary education or below) (SA4), and minimal personal solar technology adoption (5.6%) (SA5), reflecting the demographic profile typical of established rural communities experiencing large-scale renewable energy development.

Summary description of responses

In the following section, we provide a brief description of the main findings and patterns found for each research question (P). See Annex 3 for detailed summaries of all questions.

P1 - Climate Change Attitudes and Energy Transition Support

The near-universal recognition of climate change as a serious problem (96.0%) (SA6) combined with strong criticism of government climate action (62.0% disagreement) (SA7) creates favorable conditions for private renewable energy acceptance (Fig. P1). However, the gap between climate concern and energy transition support (69.6%) (SA8) suggests that recognizing climate problems does not automatically translate into renewable energy enthusiasm. This pattern indicates that climate arguments alone may be insufficient for building social acceptance, requiring complementary economic and social benefit framings to bridge the attitude-action gap.

P1A: Climate change is a very serious problem

P1B: The Portuguese government is doing enough to combat climate change

P1C: The energy transition (to renewable sources) is essential to combat climate change

Figure P1. Response distribution for P1 questions measuring general attitudes toward solar energy development. The majority of respondents agreed with statements P1A (93.3% agreement) and P1C (61.8% agreement), while showing disagreement with P1B (55.6% disagreement).

P2 - General Solar Park Opinion

The moderate positive opinion toward solar parks in general (48.5%) (SA9) represents a plurality rather than majority support, indicating cautious acceptance rather than enthusiasm (Fig. P2). This measured positivity suggests that communities approach solar technology with pragmatic assessment rather than ideological positions, creating opportunities for evidence-based persuasion but also indicating that support remains conditional on implementation quality and local benefit delivery.

P2: What is your opinion on solar parks in general?

Figure P2. Distribution of general opinions about solar energy installations (P2). Results show predominantly positive attitudes, with most respondents expressing favorable or very favorable views toward solar energy development.

P3 - Local Solar Park Knowledge

The remarkably high awareness of local solar installations (81.3% with visual contact) (SA10) ensures that community opinions are grounded in actual rather than hypothetical experiences with large-scale renewable energy infrastructure (Fig. P3). This experiential knowledge base provides legitimacy to community assessments while also meaning that any negative experiences with existing projects could significantly influence future acceptance patterns.

P3: Are you aware of any existing or under construction solar park(s) near your area of residence?

Figure P3. Level of awareness and visibility of local solar installations. Responses indicate varying degrees of familiarity with nearby solar projects, with most reporting regular visibility.

P4 - Local versus General Solar Park Opinion

The slight decrease in positive opinions from general (48.5%) to local solar parks (43.6%) (SA11) suggests a proximity effect where direct experience tempers initial enthusiasm (Fig. P4). This pattern suggests that visual impact, construction disruption, or unmet benefit expectations may create ongoing reservations even among communities living with existing installations.

P4: What is your opinion regarding the existing or under construction solar park(s) near your area of residence?

Figure P4. Local community opinions specifically about solar installations in respondents' immediate area. Shows the distribution of positive, negative, and neutral attitudes toward solar projects in their own locality.

P5 - Impact Perceptions and Benefit Recognition

The hierarchy of perceived benefits, ranging from regional development (62.8%, SA12) and energy independence (61.8%, SA13) at the top, to individual quality of life at the bottom (43.2%, SA17), suggests scale-dependent acceptance patterns, where collective goods are valued more highly than personal gains (Fig. P5). At the same time, the acknowledgment of both benefits and conflicts (with 63.8% agreeing that solar parks generate local conflicts, SA16) reflects a nuanced cost–benefit assessment, indicating that respondents recognize the complexity of solar development rather than adopting simplistic pro- or anti-development positions.

- P5A: Increases Portugal’s energy independence
- P5B: Is important for the development of the Region/Municipality
- P5C: Is important for the Local/Municipality economy
- P5D: Provides fair benefits at the Local/Municipality level
- P5E: Generates conflicts with local interests and priorities
- P5F: Improves the quality of life in the Local/Municipality
- P5G: Improves your individual or family quality of life
- P5H: Helps to combat climate change
- P5I: Could make electricity cheaper
- P5J: Could have harmful effects on flora, fauna, and ecological balance

Figure P5. Perceived impacts of solar installations across multiple dimensions (P5A-P5J). Results reveal mixed perceptions, with strong agreement on energy independence and climate benefits, but concerns about local conflicts and agricultural impacts.

P6 - Impact Expectations and Future Concerns

The mixed expectations about solar park consequences, with highest expectations for property value increases (65.1%) but lowest for personal energy savings (39.3%) (SA20, SA21), reflect uncertainty about how macro-level renewable energy benefits translate into tangible local advantages (Fig. P6). The significant expectation of negative landscape impacts (58.8%; SA20) alongside economic benefits indicates that communities anticipate trade-offs rather than uniformly positive outcomes.

- P6A: Job creation in the Region/Municipality
- P6B: Increase in land/housing prices in the Region/Municipality
- P6C: Attraction of new residents to the Region/Municipality
- P6D: Attraction of new investments to the Region/Municipality
- P6E: Negative ecological effects
- P6F: Improvement of infrastructure and facilities in the Region/Municipality
- P6G: Negative impacts on the landscape
- P6H: Improvement of quality of life in the Region/Municipality
- P6I: Reduction in the value of your monthly energy bill

Figure P6. Expected future impacts of solar installations on various local factors. Respondents anticipate both positive outcomes (energy security, environmental benefits) and potential negative consequences (landscape changes, land use conflicts).

P7 - Renewable Energy Technology Preferences

The dramatic variation in support across renewable energy types, from 29.7% for large-scale solar to 71.1% for small-scale wind (SA22), reveals that scale and technology interact to shape acceptance patterns (Fig. P7). The strong preference for distributed systems (65.3% support for residential solar; SA22) suggests that communities value local control and direct benefits over utility-scale developments.

- P7A. Future large-scale solar parks
- P7B. Future small-scale solar parks
- P7C. Solar panels on homes and warehouses
- P7D. Small-scale wind farms

Figure P7. Support levels for different types of solar energy technologies. Shows preferences between large-scale solar farms, small-scale distributed systems, rooftop installations, and community solar projects.

P8 - Municipal Priorities

The distribution of responses indicates that economic development is the most frequently selected municipal priority (n = 347; SA23), followed by environmental sustainability (n = 291) and infrastructure-related concerns (Fig. P8). This pattern suggests that economic considerations are highly salient for a large share of respondents, but not uniquely dominant, as multiple priorities are simultaneously emphasized. Importantly, respondents were able to select more than one objective, meaning that these results reflect the breadth of concerns rather than a strict hierarchy of preferences. The relatively high selection of environmental sustainability alongside economic development indicates that communities do not frame these dimensions as mutually exclusive. Overall, the findings suggest that rural communities evaluate renewable energy projects through a combination of economic, environmental, and service-related considerations, rather than primarily through a single lens.

- P8A: Economic development
- P8B: Quality of public schools
- P8C: Management of population growth or decline
- P8D: Environmental sustainability
- P8E: Maintenance of roads and transport services
- P8F: Provision of public services (e.g., waste/recycling)
- P8G: Helping to achieve national strategic goals

Figure P8. Percentage (or number) of respondents selecting each objective as a municipal priority. Respondents could select multiple objectives; therefore, values do not sum to 100%.

P9 - Solar Parks' Impact on Municipal Priorities

The relationship between selected municipal priorities and perceived solar park contributions reveals both alignment and disconnection (Fig. P9): while solar parks receive strong positive assessment for the top priority of economic development (58.4%) (SA24a), they receive weak assessment for the second priority of school quality (31.0%) (SA24b). This pattern suggests that renewable energy projects succeed in delivering some community priorities while failing to address others, creating mixed acceptance patterns.

- P9A. Economic development
- P9B. Quality of public schools
- P9C. Management of population growth or decline
- P9D. Environmental sustainability
- P9E. Maintenance of roads and transport services
- P9F. Provision of public services (e.g., waste/recycling)
- P9G. Achieve national strategic goals

Figure P9. Importance ratings on to what extent solar parks harm or help different priorities.

P10 - Planning Process Evaluation

The systematic failures in public participation, with over two-thirds unable to participate in meetings (68.4%) or transmit concerns (68.7%) (SA25, SA26), represent a fundamental breakdown in democratic decision-making that undermines legitimacy regardless of project outcomes (Fig. P10). These procedural deficits create conditions for reluctant acceptance where communities may support project outcomes while condemning the processes that produced them.

- P10A. I was able to participate in public meetings about the process
- P10B. The solar park developer tried to listen to and involve the local community
- P10C. The Municipal Council / Parish Council tried to listen to and involve the local community
- P10D. I was able to express my concerns about the solar park before it was approved
- P10E. I was given enough information about the solar park before it was approved
- P10F. The solar park developer did not keep the promises made during the planning process
- P10G. The decisions made by government officials about the solar park were in the best interest of our community
- P10H. The planning process associated with this solar park was transparent and fair

Figure P10. Evaluation of public participation processes in solar project development (P10A-P10H). Results indicate varying satisfaction levels with information access, consultation opportunities, and decision-making transparency.

P11 - Planning Process Effects on Perceptions

The predominantly neutral effects of planning processes on solar energy perceptions (64.3% no effect) and park-specific opinions (63.9% no effect) (SA30, SA31) provide crucial evidence for a ‘participation paradox’, demonstrating that communities can maintain stable substantive attitudes despite experiencing severe procedural failures (Fig. P11). This separation of process and outcome evaluations suggests resilient support for renewable energy technology even when implementation processes are problematic.

P11A. Perception of solar energy

P11B. Perception of this particular park

P11C. Trust in municipal technicians and political decision-makers

P11D. Trust in central government technicians and political decision-makers

Figure P11. Reported effects of participation processes on attitudes toward solar energy. Shows whether engagement in consultation processes led to more positive, negative, or unchanged views about solar development.

P12 - Future Development Priorities

The strong consensus around process improvements, led by scale discussions (75.2%), participation opportunities (74.9%), and communication (74.3%) (SA34), reveals that communities prioritize procedural justice over distributive benefits when designing better approaches to renewable energy development (Fig. P12). The ranking of governance improvements above financial compensation indicates that rural communities value agency and inclusion more than monetary benefits.

- P12A. Have greater communication with the local population
- P12B. Have more opportunities for local population participation in the process
- P12C. Have a mediator to manage interaction between the local population and the solar park developer
- P12D. Have more discussion about individual compensation measures
- P12E. Have more discussion about compensation measures for the municipality
- P12F. Pay dividends to all residents of the municipality where the solar park is located
- P12G. Create reductions in the energy/electricity bills for all residents of the municipality where the solar park is located
- P12H. Prioritize the integration of solar panels with other land uses
- P12I. Discuss and even limit the scale of solar parks

Figure P12. Importance ratings for various factors in solar project evaluation. Reveals which considerations (economic, environmental, social) respondents prioritize when assessing solar installations.

P13 - Cost-Benefit Assessment

The high neutrality across all cost-benefit evaluation options (SA35, SA36, SA37) indicates significant uncertainty about how to weigh multiple types of impacts, namely economic, environmental, social, and procedural, into coherent overall assessments (Fig. P13). This ambivalence reflects the complexity of renewable energy trade-offs and suggests that communities need better frameworks for integrated impact assessment rather than simple benefit-cost calculations.

P13A. The harms of the solar park are largely outweighed by the benefits it generates
P13B. The harms of the solar park are equal to the benefits it generates
P13C. The harms of the solar park are significantly greater than the benefits it generates

Figure P13. Cost-benefit assessments of solar energy development. Shows how respondents weigh the economic advantages against potential disadvantages of solar installations.

P14 - Land Suitability Preferences

The clear preference hierarchy - from unproductive agricultural land (89.8% suitable) to productive farmland (26.3% suitable) (SA38, SA39) - reflects a nuanced awareness of land-use trade-offs and a preference for renewable energy development that minimizes disruption to existing economic activities (Fig. P14). This pattern indicates that siting decisions play a decisive role in shaping social acceptance, with projects located on previously used or degraded land likely to encounter less resistance than those requiring the conversion of active farmland.

- P14A. Former waste landfill sites
- P14B. Former industrial parks
- P14C. Around existing industrial parks
- P14D. Publicly owned land (State)
- P14E. Unproductive agricultural land
- P14F. Productive agricultural land
- P14G. Forest land

Figure P14. Suitability ratings for different types of land use for the installation of solar parks.

P15 - Alternative land use types to solar farms

The moderate acceptance of traditional agricultural alternatives (37-47% adequate) (SA40) reveals that communities do not automatically view agriculture as superior to solar parks, challenging romanticized assumptions about rural land use preferences (Fig. P15). The slight preference for intensive olive groves (46.5%) and almond groves (46.3%) over hunting reserves (37.7%) suggests that productive, economically viable land uses are preferred over extensive activities. This pattern indicates that agricultural displacement by solar parks may face less resistance than expected, particularly when compensation or alternative economic opportunities are provided.

P15A: Intensive olive grove
P15B: Almond grove
P15C: Hunting reserve

Figure P15. Acceptance of alternative land use types

P16 - Value Assessment Across Categories

The remarkable consistency of intensive olive grove preferences across all value categories, from economic (47.7%) to conservation (42.6%) to cultural integration (42.1%) (SA41), demonstrates that communities seek land use options that deliver multiple benefits simultaneously rather than accepting trade-offs between different values (Fig. P16). This holistic evaluation framework suggests that successful renewable energy development must address economic, environmental, and cultural concerns in integrated approaches rather than focusing on single benefit dimensions.

P16A: Greatest economic value
P16B: Best landscape fit
P16C: Highest nature conservation value
P16D: Best local cultural fit
P16E: Greatest benefits for the local population
P16F: Greatest individual benefits

Figure P16. Preferences for alternative land uses to solar parks across six evaluation criteria (economic value, landscape fit, conservation value, cultural fit, benefits for the local population, and individual benefits). Categories with less than 5% of responses are grouped under “Other.”

P17 - Complementary Land Uses (Agrivoltaic Concepts)

The clear hierarchy from nature conservation (61.5% adequate) to agricultural integration (36-39% adequate) (SA42) reveals that communities are most supportive of passive environmental co-benefits rather than productive agrivoltaic systems (Fig. P17). The strong support for conservation integration provides a promising pathway for solar development that emphasizes biodiversity enhancement and habitat creation, while the moderate skepticism about agricultural integration indicates the need for demonstration projects that prove practical viability before scaling these concepts.

- P17A: Commercial mushroom cultivation
- P17B: Beekeeping
- P17C: Sheep farming
- P17D: Agriculture
- P17E: Nature conservation

Figure P17. Reported adequacy of alternative land uses compatible with solar parks (mushroom cultivation, beekeeping, sheep farming, agriculture, and nature conservation).

P18 - Trust in Information Sources

The clear trust hierarchy, from academic researchers (67.2%) to energy companies (25.7%) (SA43, SA44), reveals that source credibility matters more than message content for building social acceptance (Fig. P18). The high trust in knowledge-based institutions compared to commercial actors suggests that university-industry partnerships leveraging academic credibility could prove more effective than direct industry communication for addressing technical concerns.

Total responses vary by question due to missing data. Percentages calculated within each question.

- P18A. University professors / researchers
- P18B. GNR / SEPNA (National Republican Guard / Nature and Environmental Protection Service)
- P18C. Civil Protection
- P18D. Municipal technicians
- P18E. Local political decision-makers
- P18F. National political decision-makers
- P18G. Non-governmental organizations
- P18H. Neighbors
- P18I. Newspapers and television
- P18J. Local associations
- P18K. Energy companies

Figure P18. Trust levels in different information sources about solar energy. Shows varying confidence in researchers, government agencies, energy companies, environmental groups, and community leaders.

P19 - Final solar farm authorization decision

The slim plurality supporting authorization (44.8%) despite extensive process criticisms (SA45) provides the strongest evidence for the participation paradox, demonstrating that communities can separate procedural failures from substantive project merits (Fig. P19). This pattern suggests that while better planning processes remain important for democratic legitimacy, outcome quality may partially compensate for procedural deficits in rural renewable energy development.

Figure P19. Support for authorizing the solar park near respondents' residence

Responses to the question of whether residents would have authorized the installation of the solar park reveal a complex interplay of support and resistance, reflecting broader tensions in the energy transition. Those who supported authorization (“YES”) typically emphasized the environmental benefits of solar energy. They described it as clean, renewable, and sustainable, highlighting its role in reducing pollution, protecting the planet, and addressing climate change. Many also viewed solar as “the future” of energy, symbolizing ecological progress. Others stressed its usefulness and necessity, framing solar as an indispensable energy source and pointing to potential reductions in electricity costs. A further set of arguments underscored local benefits, such as municipal development, financial compensation, and added value for the community. Finally, some respondents conditioned their support on appropriate siting (safe distance from housing, moderate scale) or drew on personal experience with solar panels at home to justify a positive stance.

In contrast, those who opposed authorization (“NO”) raised concerns that solar parks damage nature and rural livelihoods. A dominant theme was the cutting of trees and destruction of green areas, perceived as environmentally harmful and contradictory to conservation. Linked to this were fears of losing agricultural land, threatening farming and grazing practices. Many respondents also stressed the visual and cultural impacts, arguing that solar farms spoil the landscape and reduce the beauty of rural areas, thereby undermining local quality of life. Opposition was further fuelled by a sense of economic unfairness, with respondents pointing to the absence of local compensation, lower bills, or tangible community benefits. Some framed solar parks as projects serving external economic interests while offering little to host communities. Additional objections included proximity to housing, large-scale developments, health concerns, and the belief that solar should instead be installed on rooftops. Others criticized the lack of information and participation, reinforcing distrust in the process.

Taken together, these findings illustrate that both support and opposition are rooted in rational and value-based reasoning. Supporters emphasize environmental sustainability, utility, and potential community gains, while opponents highlight ecological damage, loss of farmland, unfair distribution of costs and benefits, and procedural injustices. The contrast suggests that acceptance of large-scale solar projects depends not only on their technical performance but also on how they are integrated into local landscapes, economies, and governance structures.

Are there differences across regions?

To explore the structure of community perceptions across solar projects, we applied Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) as a multivariate ordination technique, allowing complex attitudinal patterns to be summarized in a reduced-dimensional space. Prior to analysis, data quality was addressed through systematic screening of missing values, ensuring that only variables with sufficient completeness and reliability were retained for ordination. Variables with more than 10% missing responses were excluded from the initial pool of variables, and remaining missing values were imputed with column medians to maximize sample retention. After this screening, 12 variables were retained for NMDS analysis: core acceptance (P2, P4), technology preferences (P7A–D), process evaluations (P10A, P10D, P10E), and information trust (P18A, P18C, P18D). Together, these variables captured outcome attitudes, technological orientation, participatory experience, and institutional trust — dimensions central to understanding social acceptance of renewable energy projects.

The NMDS ordination on this dataset converged on a two-dimensional solution with a stress value of 0.167, which represents a fair approximation of the underlying multidimensional dissimilarities. While three- (stress = 0.113) and four-dimensional solutions (stress = 0.089) provided better statistical fit, the two-dimensional configuration was retained as the most interpretable and communicable representation of community perceptions. Shepard plots confirmed adequate goodness-of-fit, with observed distances closely tracking ordination distances. Environmental vector fitting (envfit) identified several variables strongly correlated with the ordination axes (all $p < 0.001$).

NMDS1 (XX axis) aligns primarily with core acceptance and support variables, including overall authorization (P2), local opinion of the solar park (P4), and support for large-scale solar (P7A–D; Fig. 2). Negative loadings indicate increasing scepticism or opposition, while positive values reflect stronger acceptance and support. NMDS2 (YY axis) is structured mainly by process-related perceptions, especially municipal involvement (P10A), opportunities to voice concerns (P10D), and procedural fairness (P10E). Negative values correspond to higher evaluations of participatory quality, whereas positive values reflect perceived deficits (Fig. 2). A secondary gradient is visible along information trust variables (P18A, P18C, P18D), which orient diagonally and suggest that higher trust in researchers and local information sources is associated with more positive positions on both axes. Together, these axes reveal a dual structure of acceptance: NMDS1

reflects substantive evaluation of solar projects (benefits versus opposition), while NMDS2 captures procedural and institutional trust dimensions.

Figure 2. NMDS1 (XX axis) reflects core acceptance and support (P2, P4, P7A, 7B, 7D), ranging from opposition (negative values of axis) to strong support (positive values of axis). NMDS2 (YY axis) captures process perceptions (P10A, P10D, P10E), contrasting higher participatory quality (negative values of axis) with perceived deficits (positive values of axis). Information trust (P18A, P18C, P18D) adds a diagonal gradient linking researcher/local trust to more positive positions. Together, the axes distinguish substantive evaluations of solar projects from procedural and institutional trust dimensions.

Regional patterns and group tests

Although the ordination ellipses for the four regional groups (Upper North, North, Center, South) overlapped in two-dimensional space (Fig. 2), PERMANOVA detected significant differences in multivariate response profiles ($F = 30.45$, $**p < 0.001$). This suggests that community perceptions would not be randomly distributed but vary across regions. However, PERMDISP showed that these

differences are partly driven by unequal within-group dispersion. Specifically, the Upper North region exhibited significantly greater heterogeneity in responses compared to Center, North, and South (Tukey pairwise tests, all $p < 0.001$). No significant differences were found between North, Center, and South groups. This indicates that the Upper North does not cluster tightly but instead contains a wide diversity of views, from strong support to pronounced opposition. Overall, the NMDS results highlight two main dimensions of community perceptions: acceptance (benefit recognition vs. opposition) and procedural trust (participation and information quality). Regional comparisons revealed statistically significant differences, with the Upper North distinguished more by its internal diversity of attitudes than by a clear separation from other regions.

Discussion

This study of rural Portuguese communities reveals patterns of social acceptance toward large-scale PV park development that challenge conventional assumptions about renewable energy transitions in rural settings. Rather than simple acceptance or rejection, communities demonstrate nuanced evaluation frameworks that separate procedural criticism from substantive support, emphasize economic development considerations when evaluating PV parks, and show openness to innovative land-use integration when practical viability is demonstrated. The analysis is primarily based on descriptive statistics, which limits the ability to formally test relationships between variables or identify causal drivers of public acceptance. As such, the findings should be interpreted as indicative patterns rather than causal relationships. While the results provide robust insights into overall perceptions and response patterns, future research could build on this work by applying inferential methods (e.g., regression or multivariate modelling) to further explore the determinants of acceptance and their relative importance. Nevertheless, the survey analysis highlights four key themes that have significant implications for both energy democracy theory and renewable energy planning practice.

A participatory paradox?

The most striking finding in this study is the systematic disconnection between how respondents evaluate decision-making processes and how they judge project outcomes. Despite widespread

criticism of PV parks-planning, with over two thirds of respondents stating they could not participate in meetings (SA25), express their concerns (SA26), or access sufficient information (SA27), almost half of the respondents would nevertheless authorize the construction of the PV park (SA45). This participatory paradox (Parvin, 2021) challenges linear models of social acceptance that assume that only well-designed processes can automatically generate higher acceptance of these projects. Instead, our study shows that communities are able to separate evaluations of process from evaluations of substance when determining their stance towards PV parks.

The consistency of attitudes in the face of procedural shortcomings reinforces this interpretation. Most respondents reported that flaws in the planning process did not alter their overall perception of solar energy or their opinion of the specific PV park near them (SA30, SA31). This suggests that rural communities may operate with different democratic expectations than those often assumed in the energy governance literature. A substantial number of respondents appear to prioritize tangible outcomes, such as energy provision, community benefits, or proper siting, over formal consultation procedures. This may reflect a pragmatic worldview that places emphasis on results, especially in expert-based technical decisions. However, this should not be taken as indifference to democratic participation.

Paradoxically, there was also a strong demand for future improvements, particularly regarding project scale, opportunities for community involvement, and better communication (SA34). The key insight to draw here is that procedural weaknesses do not necessarily doom PV projects if outcomes align with community priorities. Yet they may generate a form of “frustrated acceptance” that remains fragile, becoming unstable if promised benefits fail to materialize or if flawed processes are seen as the norm. If we acknowledge the scale of the energy transition yet to be fulfilled these are critical warning signs that if left unattended may become a hard hindrance to manage. For example, the growing opposition in Spain toward new PV farms signals that energy transition must better balance production with land stewardship, agricultural preservation, and community interests (López-Bravo et al., 2024; Rodríguez-Segura et al., 2023).

Notwithstanding, our research findings widely resonate with existing research. According to our systematic review, studies consistently identify transparent communication, early and meaningful community participation, and trust-building as pivotal for securing social license to operate large PV parks (Bessette et al., 2024; Sato and Ngoc, 2024; Tsoeu-Ntokoane et al., 2024). The role of procedural justice is emphasized in mitigating perceptions of rural burden and

distributive injustice, which are key PV parks-opposition drivers (Hazrati, 2024; Nilson and Stedman, 2023). In addition, benefit-sharing mechanisms, including community benefit agreements, are shown to influence acceptance positively when aligned with local values (Trandafir et al., 2023). Ultimately, the sustainability of PV projects is dependent on the extent of host communities' involvement, acceptance, and trust (Tsoeu-Ntokoane et al., 2024).

What our research brings under the spotlight is that legitimacy in rural energy transitions evolves through multiple pathways beyond a singular reliance on procedural justice. Rural communities demonstrate a complex political agency by separating process criticism from outcome assessment, refusing to reject perceived beneficial PV projects solely due to flawed implementation procedures. However, this is a fragile status quo. Ignoring community concerns on procedural, representative and distributive justice, risks sparking gridlock scenarios in future PV developments undermining State legitimacy in steering a desired energy transition.

PV projects as local economic development?

Economic development emerges as the most frequently selected municipal priority among respondents, indicating its high salience in rural community expectations regarding PV projects (SA23). However, because respondents could select multiple priorities, this result reflects the breadth of concerns rather than a strict hierarchy of preferences. Environmental sustainability is also widely selected, suggesting that communities simultaneously value economic and environmental outcomes rather than viewing them as competing objectives. This pattern provides important context for understanding solar park acceptance. Respondents tend to perceive stronger or more tangible economic benefits associated with PV projects (e.g., regional development, local economy; SA13, SA14) compared to environmental benefits (e.g., climate action; SA18). However, this does not imply weaker environmental values, as evidenced by the near-universal recognition of climate change as a serious problem (SA6). Instead, it reflects differences in how benefits are perceived and experienced at the local level. At the same time, important gaps emerge between community priorities and perceived project contributions. For instance, school quality—although selected by a substantial share of respondents—receives relatively weak positive assessment in terms of PV park impacts (SA24b). This mismatch suggests a potential vulnerability for long-term acceptance if communities perceive that solar development does not adequately address locally relevant needs. These findings indicate that sustainable social acceptance depends not only on delivering economic benefits, but also on aligning renewable energy projects

with the broader set of community priorities. Interestingly, national strategic objectives—although selected less frequently as local priorities—are more positively associated with PV park impacts (SA24a). This suggests that rural communities are able to recognize broader societal benefits even when these are not central to their immediate concerns, reflecting an awareness of multi-scale governance dynamics. However, this also reinforces the importance of grounding renewable energy development in locally meaningful outcomes rather than relying primarily on national-level arguments.

Overall, these findings are consistent with existing literature highlighting the importance of economic considerations in shaping public evaluations of large-scale solar projects (Nilson and Stedman, 2023; Trandafir et al., 2023). However, they also nuance this perspective by showing that economic salience coexists with strong environmental concern and broader governance expectations. Comparative studies further indicate that environmental concerns—such as biodiversity loss or land degradation—become more prominent when economic benefits are uncertain or unevenly distributed (Hazrati, 2024). This underscores the importance of aligning renewable energy strategies with local priorities and ensuring that perceived benefits are both tangible and equitably distributed.

Scale matters

There is a scale-dependent acceptance that extends beyond solar technology to general principles about appropriate development models. While less than one third of respondents support future large-scale solar parks (SA22), their support increases dramatically for small-scale installations, doubling to two thirds for residential solar panels (SA22). Small-scale wind energy receives the highest support, indicating that scale rather than technology type primarily drives acceptance patterns. This scale-sensitivity suggests a preference for distributed systems which value local control and direct benefits over utility-scale developments that may reproduce traditional center-periphery power relations. The proximity effect provides additional evidence, with daily viewers showing lower acceptance rates compared to occasional viewers (SA46), indicating that visual exposure may hinder enthusiasm rather than build adaptation through familiarity.

Local land use preferences reinforce scale politics while revealing a complex understanding of development trade-offs. Strong support for development on unproductive agricultural land contrasts sharply with opposition to productive farmland conversion (SA38, SA39),

hinting at a nuanced reasoning about economic and environmental opportunity costs. The preference hierarchy, from degraded agricultural lands to productive agriculture areas, suggests that location decisions significantly influence social acceptance independently of technology choices. The alternative land use analysis (P15-P17) provides additional insight into scale and compatibility preferences. Studies show that integrated systems which allow simultaneous agricultural production and solar energy generation are generally viewed more favourably than conventional utility-scale solar farms (Gorjian et al., 2022; Pascaris et al., 2021).

However, in this study, moderate acceptance of agricultural alternatives to solar parks (SA40) suggests communities do not automatically view traditional agriculture as superior to renewable energy infrastructure. In fact, the strong support for conservation integration with solar parks (SA42) compared to productive agrivoltaic integration indicates openness to innovative approaches when environmental rather than economic co-benefits are emphasized. This pattern suggests that framing solar development as conservation enhancement rather than agricultural replacement may increase local social acceptance (Ascensão et al., 2023; Nordberg and Schwarzkopf, 2023). In short, surveyed rural communities display openness to innovative land-use configurations that preserve local economic activities, suggesting that agrivoltaics and/or conservoltaic could shift acceptance hierarchies by reconciling scale-sensitive conflicts.

Finally, consistent with existing research, concerns about visual impacts and ecological consequences remain (Sirnik et al., 2024), reinforcing that technological innovation alone is not sufficient to overcome resistance without addressing landscape and cultural expectations. In fact, the literature consistently finds that visual and symbolic impacts are among the most powerful drivers of opposition to solar farms (Sirnik et al., 2024; Torma and Aschemann-Witzel, 2023). These concerns go beyond aesthetics, reflecting deeper meanings tied to identity, heritage, and rural livelihoods (Moore et al., 2022). Addressing them requires more than technical mitigation; it calls for institutional innovation that grants rural communities' agency in shaping how renewable infrastructures interact with their landscapes.

Rural agency and institutional innovation

The study findings challenge both romanticized and dismissive views of rural communities in energy transitions, revealing engaged and discerning stakeholders with legitimate governance expectations rather than passive infrastructure recipients. The combination of strong benefit recognition and process criticism suggests that rural residents are not anti-development but rather

demand meaningful inclusion in procedural and distributive decisions affecting their communities. The high proportion of long-term residents (75.9% living 30+ years in their areas) (SA3) indicates deep place attachment and local knowledge that could inform better planning processes, but current institutional arrangements fail to capture this expertise.

The institutional-trust hierarchy reveals strategic opportunities for improving energy democracy through credible knowledge brokers. Academic researchers and technical experts enjoy the highest credibility (SA43), while energy companies rank lowest (SA44), suggesting that university-industry partnerships leveraging academic credibility could prove more effective than direct industry communication. The moderate-trust in local technical experts and associations (SA43) indicates that community-based organizations and local government technical staff could play important mediating roles between external developers and local residents.

A review of future development priorities, unveiled by the survey, provides a roadmap for institutional innovation in rural energy governance. Communities prioritize procedural improvements over financial compensation, with the lowest support going to direct payments despite it still representing a strong majority approval (SA34). This suggests that rural communities value agency and inclusion more than monetary benefits, contradicting assumptions that acceptance can be mainly bought through compensation schemes. The demand for scale discussions, participation opportunities, and mediated interaction indicates support for collaborative governance models that respect and include local expertise while addressing technical constraints. The strong support for conservation integration (SA42) suggests that environmental co-benefits may provide more promising pathways than agricultural productivity claims. The moderate scepticism about productive agricultural integration indicates the need for demonstration projects that address practical concerns about implementation viability rather than principled opposition to dual land use concepts.

Is there solar *NIMBYism*?

The results and patterns found in our study collectively illustrate that rural communities are active political agents capable of sophisticated evaluation of complex trade-offs rather than passive recipients of energy infrastructure. The findings fundamentally challenge the "Solar NIMBY" concept, revealing that what appears as simple "Not In My Backyard" opposition actually represents a far more complex phenomenon of rural energy governance (Stadelmann-Steffen and Dermont, 2021). The participation paradox alone, where nearly half of the interviewed citizens

would authorize construction despite overwhelming procedural criticism, demonstrates that proximity-based opposition models fail to capture the nuanced reasoning rural communities employ when evaluating renewable energy development.

Rather than exhibiting implicit or explicit NIMBYism, these communities are likely to evaluate projects across multiple criteria including procedural, representative and distributive justice, economic alignment with local priorities, scale appropriateness, and institutional credibility. The scale sensitivity findings, where support varies from 29.7% for large-scale solar to 71.1% for small-scale wind (SA22), indicate that opposition may reflect preferences for different development models rather than a fundamental technology-aversion.

Similarly, the strong support for conservation integration (SA42) alongside moderate acceptance of agricultural alternatives (SA40) suggests communities are open to innovative land use approaches when benefits are demonstrated and concerns are addressed. What we observe is a pattern of “informed conditional acceptance” where communities apply nuanced evaluation frameworks that incorporate local knowledge, place attachment, democratic expectations, and pragmatic benefit assessment. This aligns closely with the reviewed literature, which emphasizes that procedural and representative justice (i.e. transparent communication, fair participation, and opportunities to be heard), and distributive justice (the equitable allocation of costs and benefits), are the decisive dimensions of social acceptance (Hazrati, 2024; Nilson and Stedman, 2022) . In our research, despite widespread criticism of consultation processes, nearly half of respondents would still authorize solar projects, reflecting a conditional acceptance stance rather than an entrenched opposition one. Such outcomes suggest that resistance often stems from perceived injustice, not an inherent rejection of renewables. By situating opposition within the frameworks of procedural, representative and distributive justice, it becomes clear that community resistance is not an inevitable barrier but a preventable and correctable governance failure.

In sum, sustainable rural energy transitions require a political change and subsequent institutional and procedural innovations that acknowledges local communities as genuine partners with legitimate governance expectations, local knowledge, and capacity for thoughtful judgment about appropriate energy transitions development pathways. The participation paradox, economic development primacy, scale sensitivity, and institutional trust patterns provide specific guidance for designing more effective, just and democratic approaches to renewable energy development in rural contexts – approaches that recognize rural agency and discernment rather than dismissing rural concerns as simple oppositionism.

Policy Recommendations

Re-thinking the politics of energy transition

With the rapid expansion of PV farms across Portugal, similar dynamics to those observed in Spain can be anticipated, where public acceptance of utility-scale PV has recently declined (López-Bravo et al., 2024). While opposition to conventional energy systems often centers on health and environmental risks, resistance to renewables is more frequently rooted in territorial impacts and land-use conflicts (López-Bravo et al., 2024). Portugal currently benefits from a critical window of opportunity: our results show that a substantial share of residents would still authorize a PV park construction, even in the face of widespread criticism of PV park planning processes. This conditional acceptance represents a fragile but actionable basis for preventing the crystallization of a systematic “solar NIMBYism” through proactive and participatory policy design.

This window of opportunity is, nevertheless, closing fast. Today, we already witness regional divergences emerging. In particular, respondents from the northern areas (i.e. Fundão, Gavião, and Nisa) exhibited more polarized and negative positions, with a higher proportion openly opposing local PV farms. This shift suggests the beginnings of a more entrenched resistance that, if left unaddressed, could spread to other regions. Recognizing these early warning signs is essential and it turns the spotlight on governmental decision-makers. There are no known technical limitations to improve community participation, foster trust, and promote benefit-sharing. There is however a widely and conflicting debate at the political level. It is thus fundamentally a political risk to ignore the findings of this report, a risk of increasing transformation of local communities’ PV parks conditional acceptance into widespread rejection, jeopardizing Portugal’s renewable energy transition strategy.

Procedural and Representative Justice

Mandatory Early Engagement Requirements should be implemented, requiring binding and meaningful community consultation to begin at least 12 months prior to project submission. These requirements should also be key parameters for PV parks application-evaluation. These requirements must establish clear minimum standards for public meetings, including hosting multiple sessions in accessible venues and using professional facilitation to encourage broad participation. Additionally, developers should be legally obligated to provide documented

evidence showing how community input directly influenced the design and planning of the PV project.

To support fair and balanced conflict resolution, **Independent Mediation Services** should be established. These offices would offer third-party arbitration services to address disputes between developers and local communities, ensuring that all voices are heard and conflicts are resolved impartially. To maintain their independence from both industry and government influence, these services should be funded through mandatory developer fees.

To promote accountability and public trust, **Enhanced Information Transparency** measures must be adopted. This includes mandating comprehensive impact assessments that evaluate environmental, economic, visual, and social consequences of proposed projects. All technical documents should be accompanied by plain-language summaries to ensure accessibility for the general public. Additionally, online portals must be established to provide real-time access to project information, including environmental monitoring data during and after construction, enabling communities to stay informed and engaged throughout the project lifecycle.

Rationale: Our study found that 68.7% of respondents felt unable to transmit concerns and 66.2% received insufficient information, yet these procedural failures did not doom projects when outcomes aligned with community priorities.

Distributive Justice

To ensure fair and lasting returns for host communities, **Community Benefit Agreements** must be made a legal requirement for all utility-scale renewable energy projects. These agreements should be **negotiated directly with affected communities** rather than imposed by developers, and must provide benefits that last the full **operational lifetime** of the project—typically 25 to 30 years.

To maximize local economic development, policies should mandate **local hiring requirements** during both the construction and maintenance phases. In addition, developers must **procure goods and services from local suppliers** where technically feasible. A portion of project revenues should be directed into **community investment funds** that support public infrastructure, education, and other priorities identified by the host region.

Communities should also receive direct energy cost benefits from nearby projects. Mechanisms such as **discounted electricity rates, energy bill credits based on proximity**, and the formation of **community energy purchasing cooperatives** linked to local production can ensure that residents experience tangible financial advantages from hosting clean energy infrastructure.

Rationale: Economic development was the most frequently selected municipal priority, with 58.4% of respondents believing solar parks contribute to this goal.

Territorialized Scale-Sensitive Approach

To avoid over-concentration of large-scale projects, a **Cumulative Impact Assessment Framework** should be required. This includes conducting regional carrying capacity studies before approving multiple utility-scale installations and establishing maximum density thresholds within defined geographic zones. “Solar saturation” metrics must be developed to evaluate cumulative visual impact, grid constraints, landscape impacts and local acceptance, ensuring new developments align with community and ecological limits.

Recognizing strong public preference for smaller-scale energy, policy should **prioritize distributed solar** (residential and commercial) where technically and economically feasible. Incentives must be enhanced for **community-owned renewable energy projects**, empowering local stakeholders and retaining economic benefits locally. The creation of “**solar districts**”, where multiple small-scale systems replace large centralized facilities, can align renewable deployment with local values and spatial contexts.

To promote land-sharing solutions, **agrivoltaic and conservoltaic systems** should be supported through preferential permitting and targeted financial incentives. Funding for pilot projects is essential to demonstrate successful integration of agriculture and/or conservation with solar energy. Technical standards and best practices should be developed for diverse crop-solar combinations and conservation of ecosystems, helping scale up this dual-use model that balances food security, conservation and clean energy.

Rationale: Public support drops sharply from 71.1% for small-scale wind to 29.7% for large-scale solar, highlighting scale sensitivity as a critical acceptance factor.

Landscape Integration Standards

To minimize land-use conflict and protect valued spaces, a strict **siting hierarchy** should be enforced that legally prioritizes **degraded areas** and **previously disturbed sites** over undeveloped agriculture and grassland areas. Any proposed conversion of **productive agricultural land** and **protected areas** must require clear and compelling justification. **Buffer zones** must also be

established around residential areas, cultural heritage sites, and sensitive landscapes to protect quality of life and regional identity.

To mitigate visual disruption, developers must incorporate **professional landscape architecture** into the design of all utility-scale solar projects. Where feasible, projects should include **screening vegetation**, make use of **topographic integration**, and follow **design standards** for panel height, colour, and materials that are visually compatible with rural or natural contexts.

Safeguarding cultural heritage is essential. **Cultural landscape assessments** should be a required component of environmental impact studies, ensuring that development avoids areas of **high cultural or historical significance**. Where appropriate, projects should seek to **integrate traditional land use patterns** and respect the spatial character of rural or Indigenous territories.

Rationale: A significant 89.8% of respondents support solar development on **unproductive agricultural land**, while only 26.3% approve of projects on **productive farmland**. Additionally, 58.8% anticipate **negative visual impacts**, emphasizing the importance of thoughtful siting and landscape integration.

Trust-building Communication Approach

Building public trust in renewable energy requires independent, credible, and locally relevant information. Governments should **fund university-based renewable energy centers** to serve as trusted sources. Training should also be provided for **local government staff** to strengthen technical capacity and improve public communication. Long-term **academic-community partnerships** can facilitate ongoing research and strengthen transparency.

Peer-driven knowledge exchange should be promoted through **community learning programs**. These could include **visits to successful solar installations**, the formation of **regional peer networks** of solar host communities, and support for **local renewable energy ambassadors** who can share lived experience and dispel misinformation.

To foster ongoing dialogue, **multi-stakeholder platforms** should be created at the regional level. These **renewable energy councils** must include balanced representation from **community members, industry, and government**, with special attention to ensuring **rural voices** are heard alongside urban and corporate interests. Rather than one-time consultations, these platforms should support continuous engagement throughout the project lifecycle.

Rationale: Academic researchers enjoy significantly higher public trust (67.2%) compared to energy companies (25.7%), underlining the critical role of **independent and trusted information sources** in building and sustaining social acceptance.

Further PV Landscape-Integration

To reduce conflict and enhance community acceptance, funding should prioritize **next-generation solar technologies** that are less visually intrusive, such as **building-integrated photovoltaics** and **floating solar**. Investments should also support the **deployment of agrivoltaic systems** tailored to local farming practices, and **energy storage solutions** that improve local energy reliability and resilience.

Every solar project should include a **biodiversity enhancement plan** to support nature-positive outcomes (net gain). This includes promoting **pollinator-friendly groundcover**, integrating **native vegetation**, and designing infrastructure that supports **wildlife corridors** and **habitat restoration** alongside energy production.

To increase system flexibility and local benefits, communities should be supported in developing **smart grid infrastructure** that enables **virtual power plants**, integrating distributed and utility-scale generation. **Real-time energy data** on production and consumption should be made accessible to the public, promoting awareness and energy literacy.

Rationale: With 61.5% of respondents expressing support for **conservation-integrated solar parks**, innovation that aligns ecological and energy goals can boost social license and deliver co-benefits for people and nature.

Monitoring and Adaptive Management

To ensure ongoing accountability, all projects should be required to conduct **long-term monitoring** of **environmental, social, and economic impacts** post-construction. Results should be made public through **annual community impact reports**, verified by independent experts. **Feedback mechanisms** must also be in place to address unforeseen issues during operations.

Policymakers must embrace **adaptive governance**, regularly assessing the **effectiveness of existing policies** in maintaining public support. Regulations should be **updated in line with international best practices**, and rapid response protocols should be developed to adjust policy when early signs of public resistance emerge.

Tracking public sentiment over time is essential. Governments should implement **regular surveys** of affected communities to monitor acceptance trends. These efforts can form part of an **early warning system** that flags declining satisfaction and triggers **intervention strategies** to rebuild trust and address root causes of concern.

Rationale: The study highlights evolving and complex attitudes toward renewable energy, underscoring the need for **continuous engagement** and **responsive management**, rather than one-off consultation during early project stages.

Implementation Priorities

In the first year, governments should focus on high-impact, quickly actionable reforms. This includes establishing **legal requirements for enhanced community consultation**, mandating meaningful engagement at least 12 months before project submission. Simultaneously, **regional mediation services** should be created to offer trusted third-party facilitation and dispute resolution, ensuring community concerns are addressed fairly. A **siting hierarchy** must also be implemented immediately, prioritizing **brownfield development** and requiring clear justification for projects on productive farmland or sensitive landscapes.

Over the following 12 to 24 months, efforts should shift toward building institutional capacity. Governments, National and Local, and universities should collaborate to **launch regional information centers** that serve as independent sources of technical guidance and public education on renewable energy. Standardized **community benefit agreement templates** should be developed to help municipalities and developers negotiate fair, transparent, and binding agreements. During this phase, funding should also be allocated for **agrivoltaic and conservoltaic demonstration projects**, showcasing successful models of land-sharing between agriculture and solar energy production.

By the third year, efforts should focus on systemic alignment and integration. **Cumulative impact assessment frameworks** must be fully implemented to evaluate regional energy capacity and guide spatial planning. At the same time, **monitoring and adaptive management systems** should be established to track long-term project outcomes and allow for regulatory adjustments. Finally, governments should **create peer-to-peer learning networks**, connecting communities with

direct experience of renewable energy to those just beginning their transition, enabling knowledge exchange and shared problem-solving.

Limitations to the study

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. First, the analysis is primarily based on descriptive statistics, which limits the ability to formally test relationships between variables or identify causal drivers of public acceptance. Second, while the study captures respondents' perceptions of economic contributions and preferences for compensation and benefit-sharing mechanisms, it does not systematically characterize the specific community benefit schemes associated with each project site. The design and implementation of such schemes can vary significantly across contexts and may play an important role in shaping local acceptance. Collecting this information was beyond the scope of the project and would have required detailed, site-level data through engagement with developers and local authorities. Future research would benefit from systematically documenting and comparing different community benefit arrangements, in order to better understand how their structure, scale, and distribution influence public perceptions and acceptance of renewable energy projects. Finally, the cross-sectional nature of the survey captures perceptions at a single point in time, and does not account for how attitudes may evolve throughout different stages of project development.

Concluding Remarks

Portugal has made substantial progress in its Energy Transition over the last two decades. However, this transition is not without flaws. A large part of this progress is closely intertwined with PV parks development. Debatable decision-making choices regarding location and the business model of PV Parks have led to a growing stirring local opposition, to the extent that we may be risking the emergence of systematic solar NIMBY sentiment. This sentiment is still in the minority and its growth appears to be preventable. Our findings show that communities can support renewable energy projects even in the face of procedural failures when substantive outcomes align with local priorities. Yet, this “conditional acceptance” is fragile and may not be sustainable in the long term unless governance and justice concerns are addressed.

The policy framework outlined in this study speaks to four critical themes: i) the participatory paradox, ii) the salience of economic development alongside environmental and governance concerns, iii) the politics of project scale, and iv) the need to recognize rural agency in energy transitions. Proactive reforms in these areas would allow Portugal to maintain its renewable energy momentum while ensuring that rural communities are treated as partners rather than adversaries. The alternative, waiting until a NIMBY sentiment becomes entrenched, risks wider social resistance that could jeopardize Portugal's climate commitments and overall energy transition. The time to act is now, while conditional acceptance still prevails and communities remain willing to engage constructively.

This research contributes to energy social science by documenting rural agency and by showing the limitations of both conventional participation models and simplistic NIMBY explanations. Communities are not uniformly resistant but instead apply careful reasoning that weighs local priorities, governance quality, and potential tangible benefits. Future research should explore the stability of “frustrated acceptance” over time, assess the effectiveness of different institutional arrangements for meaningful participation, and test these results across other cultural and technological contexts.

As highlighted more than a decade ago (Sovacool, 2014), the neglect of social science perspectives in energy studies continues to hinder the inclusivity and effectiveness of the energy transition. A just and equitable shift to sustainable energy requires more than technological innovation: it demands deep engagement with the social and political dimensions that shape how energy systems are planned, accepted, and experienced (Mulvaney, 2020). Yet energy policy and research have historically privileged technical metrics over politics, human behaviour, cultural context, and community acceptance—overlooking precisely the dynamics that determine success or failure. Addressing this gap requires stronger interdisciplinary collaboration and targeted funding to support participatory research, community engagement, and longitudinal studies that track behavioural and institutional change. Without this investment, the energy transition risks reproducing existing inequalities and fuelling resistance. Bridging the divide between politics, technical expertise and social insight is not optional but foundational to building just, inclusive, and sustainable energy futures.

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Annexes

Annex 1 - Demography and other parameters of surveyed citizens

TABLE A1.1: Gender Distribution

Gender	Count	Percentage
Female	324	53.1
Male	286	46.9

TABLE A1.2: Age Distribution

Age_Group	Count	Percentage
18-24 years	43	7.0
25-34 years	62	10.2
35-44 years	77	12.6
45-54 years	89	14.6
55-64 years	116	19.0
65-74 years	145	23.8
75+ years	78	12.8

TABLE A1.3: Education Level

Education_Level	Count	Percentage
Secondary Education (10th-12th grade)	196	32.1
Primary Education Complete	155	25.4
9th grade	123	20.2
6th grade	76	12.5
University Degree	30	4.9
Primary Education Incomplete/Illiterate	21	3.4
Postgraduate/Master's/PhD	5	0.8
Technical/Polytechnic	4	0.7

TABLE A1.4: Years of Residence

Residence_Duration	Count	Percentage
Less than 10 years	42	6.9
10-30 years	105	17.2
30-50 years	173	28.4
50+ years	290	47.5

TABLE A1.5: Number of surveys per focal solar farm

Location	Count	Percentage
MOURA	100	16.4
SOLSTIDO + AMARGILHA	89	14.6
FUNDÃO (all areas)	61	10
AMARELEJA	60	9.8
OURIQUE (all areas)	60	9.8
SANTAS	40	6.6
NISA + Falagueira	40	6.6

ALCOUTIM	40	6.6
PEREIRO - FASE 1	40	6.6
DIVOR	40	6.6
HERCULES	40	6.6

Annex 2 - Detailed summary of responses

In the following section, we provide a more detailed description of the responses. These descriptions served as the basis for the discussion of the results (see below).

(P1) The following statements (in bold) were classified by respondents according to their level of agreement. "Climate change is a very serious problem". The overwhelming majority of respondents (96.0%) agree that climate change represents a serious problem (6), with 58.3% strongly agreeing. This near-universal consensus establishes a strong foundation for renewable energy acceptance, as it demonstrates widespread recognition of the environmental challenge that solar parks aim to address. Only 1.5% of respondents disagreed with this statement (6), indicating remarkable alignment on climate science across this rural Portuguese population. **"The Portuguese government does enough to combat climate change".** In stark contrast to their climate change concerns, 62.0% of respondents disagree that the Portuguese government is doing enough to combat climate change (7), with 38.9% expressing clear disagreement. Only 21.0% believe government efforts are sufficient (7). This substantial criticism suggests a perceived policy gap between the urgency of climate action and current government response, potentially creating space for greater acceptance of private renewable energy initiatives. **"Energy transition (to renewables) is fundamental to combat climate change".** A solid majority (69.6%) agree that the energy transition to renewables is fundamental for combating climate change (8), with 38.2% agreeing and many others strongly agreeing. However, this support is notably lower than the 96% who recognize climate change as serious, suggesting some respondents may favour alternative solutions or have reservations about renewable energy implementation. Nevertheless, the strong majority support provides a favourable context for solar park development.

(P2) Respondents were asked about their opinion on solar farms in general. Respondents hold moderately positive views toward solar parks in general, with 48.5% expressing positive or very positive opinions (9). This represents a plurality rather than majority support, with 21.5% holding negative views and others remaining neutral (9). The moderate positivity suggests general acceptance of solar technology while leaving room for concerns about specific implementations or local impacts.

(P3) The respondent was then asked if he/she was aware of any existing or under construction solar park(s) near his/her area of residence. The awareness of local solar parks is remarkably high, with 81.3% of respondents having some level of visual contact with nearby installations (10). Most respondents (53.3%) see the local solar park occasionally, while 28.5% encounter it daily (10). This high awareness level is crucial for the study's validity, as it ensures respondents are commenting on actual rather than hypothetical experiences with large-scale solar development.

(P4) Respondents were asked about their opinion on existing or under-construction solar park(s) near their area of residence. When asked specifically about their local solar park, positive opinions decrease slightly to 43.6% compared to 48.5% for solar parks in general (11). The most common response remains positive (41.5%), but negative views increase to 26.6% (11). This proximity effect suggests that direct experience with solar parks may temper enthusiasm, possibly due to visual impact, construction disruption, or unmet expectations about local benefits.

(P5) Regarding the solar park (existing or under construction) near their area of residence, respondents were asked to rate the following statements (in bold). "Solar park increases energy independence of Portugal". A strong majority (61.8%) agree that solar parks contribute to Portugal's energy independence (12), with 44.9% agreeing and others strongly agreeing. This represents one of the strongest support areas for solar parks, indicating that national energy security arguments resonate well with rural communities. The recognition of strategic national benefits suggests that energy independence framing could be effective in building support for future projects. **"A solar park is important for regional/municipal development"**. This sentence received the highest agreement level among impact perceptions, with 62.8% agreeing that solar parks contribute to regional and municipal development (13). More than half (54.9%) agree with this statement, indicating strong recognition that these installations can drive local economic growth. This finding suggests that development benefits represent the most compelling argument for solar parks among rural communities. **"A solar park is important for the local/municipal economy"**. Nearly 60% of respondents (59.6%) agree that solar parks benefit the local economy (14), with 47.2% expressing agreement. This strong support for economic benefits, combined with the development benefits above, indicates that rural communities primarily view solar parks through an economic development lens rather than purely environmental terms. The economic argument appears to be a key driver of acceptance. **"Solar park provides fair compensation at**

local/municipal level". Agreement on fair compensation drops to 48.9% (15), representing more moderate support than for general economic benefits. With 39.9% agreeing and 25.1% disagreeing, this issue shows more division than other economic impacts. The lower support suggests that while communities recognize economic benefits, many question whether local compensation arrangements are adequate or equitable.

"Solar parks generate conflicts with local interests and priorities". Remarkably, 63.8% of respondents agree that solar parks generate conflicts with local interests (16), with 46.1% expressing agreement. This represents one of the highest agreement levels in the survey, indicating widespread recognition that solar development creates local tensions. The acknowledgment of conflicts alongside economic benefits suggests a nuanced understanding of solar parks as both beneficial and problematic for communities.

"Solar parks improve local/municipal quality of life". Just over half of respondents (51.7%) agree that solar parks improve quality of life at the community level, with 42.4% expressing agreement. However, nearly a quarter (23.6%) disagree, showing more division on this issue. The moderate support suggests that while economic benefits are recognized, their translation into tangible quality of life improvements is less certain in residents' minds.

"Solar parks improve individual or family quality of life". This question received the lowest agreement among all impact perceptions, with only 43.2% agreeing that solar parks improve individual or family quality of life (17). The most common response was agreement (34.1%), but disagreement reached 26.9%. This finding reveals a critical gap: while communities recognize collective benefits, they see limited personal advantages from solar park development.

"Solar parks help combat climate change". Three-fifths of respondents (60.3%) agree that solar parks help combat climate change (18), with 46.6% expressing agreement. This strong support aligns with the high level of climate change concern expressed earlier. The environmental argument resonates well with rural communities, though not as strongly as economic development arguments, suggesting multiple framings may be necessary for maximum support.

"Solar parks can make electricity cheaper". Over half of respondents (55.1%) believe solar parks can reduce electricity costs, with 41.7% agreeing. However, 23.5% disagree, indicating some scepticism about whether renewable energy benefits translate into consumer savings. The moderate support suggests that energy cost arguments have appeal but may require stronger evidence or guarantees to be fully convincing.

"Solar parks may have harmful effects on flora, fauna and ecological balance". A majority (52.5%) agree that solar parks may harm local ecosystems (19), with 37.3% expressing agreement and only 18.0% disagreeing. This creates an interesting tension with climate benefits, as respondents simultaneously see solar parks as helping global climate while potentially harming local environments. This suggests environmental concerns operate at different scales in residents' thinking.

(P6) Regarding the solar park(s) (existing or under construction) near their area of residence, respondents were asked about the likelihood of various impacts. The responses reveal mixed expectations about solar park consequences, with some impacts seen as more probable than others.

"Job creation in region/municipality". Over half of respondents (54.4%) consider job creation probable or very probable (45), with 45.8% rating it as probable. This represents moderate optimism about employment benefits, though expectations are tempered compared to other economic impacts. The finding suggests that while communities expect some job creation, they may not see employment as the primary economic benefit of solar development.

"Land/housing price increases in region/municipality". Nearly two-thirds (65.1%) expect solar parks to increase property values (45), with 45.6% considering this probable. This represents the highest expectation among all P6 impacts, suggesting that communities anticipate real estate appreciation as a significant consequence of solar development. The strong expectation may reflect hope for economic benefits or concern about gentrification effects.

"Attracting new residents to the region/municipality". Less than half (46.1%) expect solar parks to attract new residents (46), with 36.4% considering this probable. The moderate expectation suggests communities are uncertain whether renewable energy infrastructure will make their areas more attractive to newcomers, possibly reflecting ambivalence about demographic change.

"Attracting new investments to the region/municipality". Just over half (53.3%) expect solar parks to attract additional investments (45), with 39.2% rating this as probable. This moderate expectation indicates that communities hope solar development will catalyse broader economic activity but remain somewhat uncertain about spill over effects.

"Negative ecological effects". Nearly half (48.1%) expect negative ecological impacts, with 35.3% considering these probable. This expectation aligns with the environmental concerns expressed

in P5J, indicating persistent worry about local ecosystem impacts despite recognition of global climate benefits.

"Infrastructure improvement in region/municipality". Less than half (46.5%) expect infrastructure improvements (46), with 39.1% rating these as probable. The moderate expectation suggests communities are uncertain whether solar parks will bring broader infrastructure benefits beyond the installations themselves.

"Negative impacts on landscape". A majority (58.8%) expect negative landscape impacts (45), with 45.7% considering these probable. This high expectation reflects significant concern about visual and aesthetic effects of large-scale solar installations, representing a key challenge for social acceptance.

"Quality of life improvement in region/municipality". Less than half (48.7%) expect quality of life improvements, with 42.7% rating these as probable. The moderate expectation aligns with the ambivalence expressed in P5F about community-level quality of life benefits.

"Reduction in monthly energy bill". Only 39.3% expect personal energy cost reductions (46), with 30.8% considering these probable. This represents the lowest expectation among all P6 impacts, indicating significant scepticism about whether solar parks will translate into direct consumer savings.

(P7) Respondents were asked about their support for installing different types of renewable energy in their region/municipality. The responses reveal a clear hierarchy of renewable energy acceptance, with smaller-scale installations receiving much higher support than large-scale developments.

"Future large-scale solar parks". Only 29.7% support future large-scale solar parks (47), while 48.3% oppose them. The most common response is opposition (30.2%). This finding reveals a significant contradiction: while respondents show moderate acceptance of existing large-scale parks, they oppose future similar developments, possibly reflecting saturation concerns or disappointment with current experiences.

"Future small-scale solar parks". Support increases dramatically to 59.2% for small-scale installations (47), with only 17.4% opposition. The most common response is support (52.5%). This stark difference suggests that scale is a crucial factor in renewable energy acceptance, with smaller installations seen as more compatible with rural communities.

"Solar panels on houses and warehouses". Support reaches 65.3% for residential and commercial solar installations (47), with only 11.4% opposition. The most common response is support (57.0%). This high acceptance indicates strong preference for distributed rather than centralized renewable energy, possibly reflecting desires for local control and direct benefits.

"Small-scale wind parks". Wind energy receives the highest support at 71.1% (47), with only 9.8% opposition. The most common response is support (56.4%). This finding suggests that concerns about large-scale solar may be technology-specific rather than reflecting general renewable energy opposition.

(P8) Respondents were asked to list municipal priority areas that local leaders should focus on.

For P8, respondents were asked to select the objectives they considered priorities for municipal leaders. As multiple selections were allowed, results were analysed as frequencies rather than ranking.

Economic development was the most frequently selected priority (n = 347), indicating its high salience among rural communities. **Environmental sustainability** was also widely selected (n = 291), followed by **maintenance of roads and transport services** (n = 254) and **population management** (n = 210). **Public services** (n = 181), **school quality** (n = 166), and **national strategic objectives** (n = 148) were selected less frequently, though still by a substantial share of respondents. This distribution suggests that rural communities hold multiple, coexisting priorities rather than a strict hierarchy of preferences. While economic development stands out as the most commonly identified concern, the relatively high selection of environmental sustainability indicates that respondents do not view economic and environmental objectives as mutually exclusive. Overall, these results point to a multidimensional set of community expectations, combining economic development, environmental considerations, and service provision, rather than a singular focus on any one domain.

(P9) Respondents evaluated whether solar parks help or harm the same municipal priorities identified in P8. The responses reveal a complex relationship between priority importance and perceived solar park contributions, with some surprising patterns emerging.

Economic development receives strong positive assessment, with 58.4% believing solar parks help (49) compared to 12.0% who see harm and 29.6% perceiving no impact. This strong alignment

between the community's highest priority and positive solar park assessment provides a crucial foundation for social acceptance.

Environmental sustainability receives the second-strongest positive assessment, with 58.9% believing solar parks help (49) compared to 13.3% who see harm and 27.8% perceiving no impact. This finding demonstrates that despite being ranked lower than economic and educational priorities, communities strongly recognize solar parks' environmental benefits.

National strategic objectives paradoxically receive the highest positive assessment, with 62.0% believing solar parks help achieve national goals (49) compared to only 5.8% who see harm and 32.2% perceiving no impact. This suggests that while communities don't prioritize national objectives for local leadership, they recognize solar parks' strategic national importance.

Public services provision received moderate positive assessment, with 51.1% believing solar parks help (49) compared to 6.2% who see harm and 42.7% perceiving no impact. This indicates communities expect some indirect benefits to public services, possibly through increased tax revenues or economic spill overs.

Road and transport maintenance show mixed assessment, with 44.7% believing solar parks help (50), 12.9% seeing harm, and 42.4% perceiving no impact. The more divided response reflects uncertainty about whether solar development generates sufficient activity to affect transport infrastructure.

Population management receives limited positive assessment, with only 37.2% believing solar parks help (50), 10.9% seeing harm, and 52.0% perceiving no impact. The predominantly neutral response suggests communities are uncertain whether solar development significantly affects demographic trends.

School quality receives the weakest positive assessment, with only 31.0% believing solar parks help (50) compared to 9.1% who see harm and 59.9% perceiving no impact. Despite education being highly prioritized, communities see limited connection between solar development and educational quality, representing a potential gap between community priorities and perceived solar benefits.

(P10) Respondents evaluated various aspects of the planning process for their local solar park.

The responses reveal systematic failures in public participation and community engagement.

"Could participate in public meetings about the process". A striking 68.4% disagree that they could participate in public meetings (20), representing one of the strongest disagreement levels in

the entire survey. Only 11.0% agree they had participation opportunities. This fundamental exclusion from formal participation channels likely contributes significantly to negative feelings about the overall process.

"Solar park promoters sought to listen to and involve the local community". Over half (56.6%) disagree that developers made genuine efforts to engage communities (23), while only 14.1% agree. This perception of inadequate private sector engagement suggests that developers focused primarily on regulatory compliance rather than meaningful community involvement, contributing to ongoing tensions.

"Municipality/Parish Council sought to listen to and involve the local community". Local government engagement received similarly poor ratings, with 54.1% disagreeing that municipal authorities adequately involved communities (24). Only 13.8% agree with this statement. This indicates that both private and public sector actors failed to meet community expectations for meaningful participation.

"Could transmit concerns about the solar park before approval". This receives the highest disagreement in the survey, with 68.7% feeling unable to express concerns before project approval (21). Only 8.7% agree they could voice concerns. This fundamental communication breakdown represents a core failure in the planning process and likely contributes significantly to negative feelings about both specific projects and the broader development process.

"Was given sufficient information about the solar park before approval". Two-thirds (66.2%) disagree that they received adequate information (22), while only 11.3% agree. This information deficit compounds the participation failures and suggests that communities felt blindsided by development decisions, undermining trust and acceptance even when projects might have benefits.

"Solar park promoters did not fulfil promises made during the planning process". Only 9.8% agree that promoters failed to keep promises, though many respondents may not have had sufficient engagement to know what promises were made. The limited reports of broken promises may reflect the minimal engagement processes described above rather than indicating good faith compliance.

"Government officials' decisions about solar parks were in the best interest of the community". A significant minority (41.1%) disagreed that government decisions served community interests, while only 12.6% agree. This scepticism about official motivations suggests that many residents

suspect decisions were made primarily to benefit developers, utilities, or national interests rather than local communities.

"The planning process associated with this solar park was transparent and fair". Over 40% (41.5%) disagree that the process was transparent and fair, while only 9.8% agree. Combined with the participation and information failures noted above, this indicates widespread perception that the decision-making process lacked integrity, creating lasting negative feelings even when project outcomes are positive.

(P11) Respondents were asked how the preparation and implementation process of the solar park affected various aspects of their perceptions and confidence. The responses reveal that the planning process had predominantly neutral effects, with most respondents reporting no change in their views or confidence levels.

"Perception of solar energy". The majority of respondents (64.3%) report that the planning process did not affect their general perception of solar energy (35), while 19.0% experienced positive effects and 16.8% negative effects. This suggests that attitudes toward solar technology as a whole remain relatively stable regardless of local implementation experiences, indicating that specific project problems do not necessarily undermine support for renewable energy broadly.

"Perception of this particular park". Similarly, 63.9% report no effect on their perception of the specific local solar park (36), with 19.4% experiencing positive effects and 16.7% negative effects. The parallel pattern suggests that even problematic planning processes may not fundamentally alter how communities view the projects themselves, supporting the participation paradox identified earlier.

"Confidence in municipal technicians and political decision-makers". Local government confidence shows slightly more positive impact, with 21.8% reporting increased confidence (37), 64.0% no change, and 14.2% decreased confidence. This relatively better performance may reflect closer community relationships with local officials or appreciation for their constrained role in centrally-driven energy policies.

"Confidence in central administration technicians and political decision-makers". Central government confidence shows the most negative pattern, with 68.5% reporting no effect (38), 18.4% positive effects, and 13.0% negative effects. The higher proportion reporting no change may reflect already low baseline expectations for central government engagement with local communities.

(P12) Respondents evaluated priorities for future solar park development processes. The responses reveal strong demand for enhanced participation and communication, with most measures receiving support from over 70% of respondents (39).

"Discuss and limit the scale of solar parks" receives the highest support at 75.2% (39), indicating that scale concerns represent the most important issue for future developments. This finding suggests that communities may accept solar development more readily if they have input into project sizing and cumulative impacts.

"More opportunities for local population participation" ranks second at 74.9% (39), directly addressing the participation deficits identified in P10. The strong support indicates communities want genuine engagement opportunities rather than token consultation processes.

"Greater communication with local population" receives 74.3% support (39), complementing the participation demands and suggesting that information deficits represent a major concern that could be addressed through improved communication strategies.

"Greater discussion about individual compensatory measures" receives 73.8% support (39), indicating interest in personalized benefit-sharing arrangements that address individual-level impacts and concerns.

"Greater discussion about compensatory measures for municipalities" receives 72.8% support (39), showing demand for community-level benefits that complement individual measures.

"Create reductions in energy/electricity bill" receives 72.6% support (39), representing strong interest in direct energy cost benefits that would provide tangible household advantages from local renewable energy development.

"Mediator to manage interaction" receives 72.3% support (39), suggesting communities recognize the value of independent facilitation to bridge differences between residents and developers.

"Privilege integration with other land uses" receives 71.0% support (39), indicating interest in agrivoltaic or other multiple-use approaches that minimize land use conflicts.

"Pay dividends to all inhabitants" receives the lowest support at 70.5% (39), though still representing strong majority approval. The relatively lower ranking suggests communities prefer participation and communication improvements over direct financial payments.

(P13) Respondents were asked to evaluate the overall cost-benefit balance of solar parks. The responses reveal significant ambivalence, with neutral positions dominating across all three assessment options.

"Harms are largely compensated by benefits" receives 30.0% agreement (40), but the most common response is neutral (45.6%), indicating uncertainty about whether benefits adequately address negative impacts.

"Harms equal the benefits" receives 23.6% agreement (41), with neutrality again dominating (47.4%). This lower agreement suggests fewer respondents see an exact balance between costs and benefits.

"Harms are largely greater than benefits" receives 32.5% agreement (42) with 42.4% neutral responses. The slightly higher agreement compared to the benefits-dominant option suggests somewhat more pessimistic than optimistic assessments, though neutrality remains the plurality position.

The high neutrality across all options indicates significant uncertainty about cost-benefit calculations, possibly reflecting the complex mix of recognized benefits and acknowledged problems identified throughout the survey.

(P14) Respondents evaluated the suitability of different land types for solar park installation.

The responses reveal clear preferences for brownfield and previously disturbed sites over productive natural or agricultural areas.

"Unproductive agricultural land" receives the highest suitability rating at 89.8% (43), indicating strong preference for utilizing land that is not economically productive for traditional agriculture.

"Old waste landfills" ranks second at 84.2% (43), demonstrating support for renewable energy development on contaminated or previously disturbed sites that provide environmental remediation benefits.

"Old industrial parks" receives 79.4% suitability rating (43), continuing the pattern of preference for redeveloping previously used industrial sites rather than converting natural areas.

"Public (State) land" receives 71.8% suitability rating (43), indicating moderate support for development on government-owned property, possibly reflecting assumptions about easier public consultation and benefit-sharing.

"Around current industrial parks" receives 69.1% suitability rating (43), suggesting acceptance of industrial area expansion for renewable energy purposes.

"Productive agricultural land" receives the lowest suitability rating at 26.3% (44), reflecting strong opposition to converting economically valuable farmland for energy purposes.

"Forest land" receives a much lower suitability rating at 43.7% (44), indicating significant concern about converting natural forest areas for solar development.

(P15) Respondents evaluated how adequate different land types would be as alternatives to the current solar park location. The responses reveal moderate acceptance of traditional agricultural alternatives, with slight preferences for established tree crops over hunting reserves.

"Intensive olive grove" receives the highest adequacy rating at 46.5% (57), indicating that nearly half of respondents view intensive olive cultivation as a reasonable alternative to solar parks. However, 30.2% consider it inadequate and 23.3% remain neutral, showing significant division on this traditional Mediterranean crop.

"Almond grove" achieves similar acceptance at 46.3% adequate (57), with lower opposition (25.1% inadequate) and higher neutrality (28.7%) compared to olive groves. This suggests almond cultivation may be less controversial as an alternative land use.

"Hunting reserve" receives the lowest adequacy rating at 37.7% (57), representing the most divisive alternative with nearly equal proportions supporting (37.7%) and opposing (35.6%) hunting reserves as preferable to solar parks. The relatively lower acceptance may reflect concerns about land access or economic productivity compared to agricultural alternatives.

(P16) Respondents were asked which alternative land type provides the greatest value across different criteria. The responses reveal a remarkably consistent preference hierarchy across all value categories assessed.

Intensive olive grove emerges as the clear preference across all six value categories (58), receiving 42-48% support for economic value (47.7%), landscape integration (43.1%), conservation value (42.6%), cultural integration (42.1%), population benefits (43.8%), and individual benefits (43.1%). This consistency suggests that communities do not perceive major trade-offs between different types of benefits—they expect the same alternative to deliver across economic, environmental, cultural, and social dimensions.

Hunting reserve consistently ranks second across most categories (10-18%), while **almond grove ranks third** (6-9%). Respondents also spontaneously mentioned additional alternatives including

cereals/grains (7-13% across categories), vineyards (1-3%), and cork oaks (1-3%), indicating broader agricultural options beyond the three provided choices.

(P18) Respondents rated their trust in various information sources about solar park projects.

The responses reveal a clear hierarchy of institutional credibility that has important implications for communication strategies.

"University professors/researchers" receive the highest trust at 67.2% (51), indicating strong confidence in academic and scientific expertise for providing reliable information about renewable energy projects.

"Civil Protection" ranks second at 63.9% (51), suggesting high confidence in emergency services organizations that are seen as protecting public interests.

"Municipality technicians" receive 59.8% trust (51), indicating moderate confidence in local government technical expertise, possibly reflecting their perceived local knowledge and accountability.

"GNR/SEPNA" (environmental police) receive 59.7% trust (51), showing confidence in specialized environmental law enforcement agencies.

"Local associations" receive 53.4% trust (51), indicating moderate confidence in community-based organizations that represent local interests.

"Neighbors" receive 53.3% trust, showing that peer-to-peer information sharing has moderate credibility within communities.

"Local political decision-makers" receive 48.4% trust (27), indicating mixed confidence in elected local officials.

"Non-governmental organizations" receive 43.6% trust (52), suggesting moderate confidence in advocacy organizations.

"Newspapers and television" receive 42.5% trust (52), indicating limited confidence in traditional media sources for technical information.

"National political decision-makers" receive 39.5% trust (52), reflecting significant scepticism about central government motivations and expertise.

"Energy companies" receive the lowest trust at 25.7% (52), indicating substantial suspicion of commercial actors' information and motivations in renewable energy development.

(P19) Respondents were asked whether they would have authorized construction of the solar park near their residence if the decision had been theirs. This final question provides the most direct measure of social acceptance despite all the process and impact concerns expressed throughout the survey.

44.8% would have authorized construction (53), representing a plurality position that indicates conditional acceptance of solar development despite widespread criticism of planning processes and mixed assessments of impacts.

40.0% would not have authorized construction (53), representing substantial opposition that reflects the various concerns about processes, impacts, and benefit distribution expressed in earlier responses.

15.2% remain undecided (53), indicating a significant group whose acceptance could potentially be influenced by improvements in project design, planning processes, or benefit-sharing arrangements.

The slim plurality in favour of authorization, despite extensive process criticisms, strongly supports the participation paradox interpretation: communities can separate procedural failures from substantive project merits, suggesting that better planning processes could significantly increase acceptance levels among currently undecided or opposed residents.

Annex 3 - Statistical appendix

All percentages are calculated based on valid responses, excluding "Don't know/No response" (NS/NR) cases unless otherwise specified. Agreement percentages combine "Agree" and "Strongly Agree" responses; disagreement percentages combine "Disagree" and "Strongly Disagree" responses. Support percentages combine "Support" and "Strongly Support" responses; opposition percentages combine "Oppose" and "Strongly Oppose" responses.

Demographic Statistics

(SA1) Gender Distribution

- Female: $324/610 = 53.1\%$
- Male: $286/610 = 46.9\%$
- Source: Variable DC2

(SA2) Mean Age

- Mean age: 54.6 years
- Median age: 58 years
- Valid responses: 610
- Source: Variable DC3

(SA3) Long-term Residence

- 30+ years residence: $463/610 = 75.9\%$
- Breakdown: 30-50 years (173) + 50+ years (290) = 463
- Source: Variable DC4 (years of residence)

(SA4) Education Level

- Secondary education or below: $474/610 = 77.7\%$
- Breakdown: Secondary (196) + Primary complete (155) + 9th grade (123) = 474
- Source: Variable DC8

(SA5) Solar Panel Adoption

- Personal solar panels: $34/610 = 5.6\%$
- No solar panels: $576/610 = 94.4\%$
- Source: Variable DC7

Climate and Energy Attitudes (P1 Series)

(SA6) Climate Change Concern

- Agreement that climate change is serious: $583/593 = 96.0\%$ (valid responses)
- Breakdown: Strongly agree (346) + Agree (237) = 583
- Disagreement: $9/593 = 1.5\%$
- Strongly agreeing: $346/593 = 58.3\%$
- Source: Variable P1A

(SA7) Government Climate Action Criticism

- Disagreement that government does enough: $339/547 = 62.0\%$ (valid responses)
- Breakdown: Strongly disagree (126) + Disagree (213) = 339
- Clear disagreement: $213/547 = 38.9\%$

- Agreement that government does enough: 115/547 = 21.0%
- Source: Variable P1B

(SA8) Energy Transition Support

- Agreement that transition is fundamental: 377/542 = 69.6% (valid responses)
- Agreeing (not strongly): 207/542 = 38.2%
- Source: Variable P1C

Solar Park General Opinions (P2-P4 Series)

(SA9) General Solar Park Opinion

- Positive opinion: 291/600 = 48.5% (valid responses)
- Breakdown: Positive (268) + Very positive (23) = 291
- Negative views: 129/600 = 21.5%
- Source: Variable P2

(SA10) Local Solar Park Knowledge

- Some visual contact: 591/610 = 81.3%
- Daily viewing: 174/610 = 28.5%
- Occasional viewing: 322/610 = 52.8%
- Rarely see it: 95/610 = 15.6%
- Source: Variable P3

(SA11) Local Solar Park Opinion

- Positive opinion: 254/583 = 43.6% (valid responses)
- Most common positive response: 41.5%
- Negative views: 155/583 = 26.6%
- Source: Variable P4

Impact Perceptions (P5 Series)

(SA12) Energy Independence Benefits

- Agreement: 315/510 = 61.8% (valid responses)
- Breakdown: Agree (229) + Strongly agree (86) = 315
- Agreeing (not strongly): 229/510 = 44.9%
- Source: Variable P5A

(SA13) Regional Development Benefits

- Agreement: 326/519 = 62.8% (valid responses)
- Breakdown: Agree (285) + Strongly agree (41) = 326
- Agreeing (not strongly): 285/519 = 54.9%
- Source: Variable P5B

(SA14) Local Economic Benefits

- Agreement: 307/515 = 59.6% (valid responses)
- Agreeing (not strongly): 243/515 = 47.2%
- Source: Variable P5C

(SA15) Fair Compensation

- Agreement: 232/474 = 48.9% (valid responses)
- Agreeing (not strongly): 189/474 = 39.9%
- Disagreement: 119/474 = 25.1%
- Source: Variable P5D

(SA16) Conflicts with Local Interests

- Agreement: 310/486 = 63.8% (valid responses)
- Agreeing (not strongly): 224/486 = 46.1%
- Source: Variable P5E

(SA17) Individual Quality of Life

- Agreement: 215/498 = 43.2% (valid responses)
- Agreeing (not strongly): 170/498 = 34.1%
- Disagreement: 134/498 = 26.9%
- Source: Variable P5G

(SA18) Climate Benefits

- Agreement: 315/522 = 60.3% (valid responses)
- Agreeing (not strongly): 243/522 = 46.6%
- Source: Variable P5H

(SA19) Environmental Concerns

- Agreement that solar parks may harm flora/fauna: 253/482 = 52.5% (valid responses)
- Agreeing (not strongly): 180/482 = 37.3%
- Disagreement: 87/482 = 18.0%
- Source: Variable P5J

Impact Expectations (P6 Series)

(SA20) Highest Expected Impacts

- Land/housing price increases: 65.1% probable (P6B)
- Negative landscape impacts: 58.8% probable (P6G)
- Job creation: 54.4% probable (P6A)
- New investments attraction: 53.3% probable (P6D)
- Source: Variables P6B, P6G, P6A, P6D (combined "Probable" + "Very Probable")

(SA21) Lowest Expected Impacts

- Reduction in monthly energy bill: 39.3% probable (P6I)
- Infrastructure improvements: 46.5% probable (P6F)
- Attracting new residents: 46.1% probable (P6C)
- Source: Variables P6I, P6F, P6C

Renewable Energy Support (P7 Series)

(SA22) Support for Different Renewable Types

- Small-scale wind parks: 71.1% support (P7D)
- Solar panels on houses/warehouses: 65.3% support (P7C)
- Small-scale solar parks: 59.2% support (P7B)
- Future large-scale solar parks: 29.7% support (P7A)
- Opposition to large-scale solar: 48.3% (P7A)
- Most common response for large-scale: Opposition (30.2%)
- Source: Variables P7D, P7C, P7B, P7A (combined "Support" + "Strongly Support")

Municipal Priorities (P8 Series)

(SA23) Municipal Priorities by Mean Rank

- Economic development: selected by 347 respondents
- Environmental sustainability: selected by 291 respondents
- Transport/roads: selected by 254 respondents

- Population management: selected by 210 respondents
- Public services: selected by 181 respondents
- School quality: selected by 166 respondents
- Source: Variables P8#1 through P8#7

Solar Parks Impact on Municipal Priorities (P9 Series)

(SA24a) Areas Where Solar Parks Most Help Municipal Priorities

- National strategic objectives: 62.0% help (P9G)
- Environmental sustainability: 58.9% help (P9D)
- Economic development: 58.4% help (P9A)
- Public services provision: 51.1% help (P9F)
- Source: Variables P9G, P9D, P9A, P9F

(SA24b) Areas Where Solar Parks Least Help Municipal Priorities

- School quality: 31.0% help, 59.9% no impact (P9B)
- Population management: 37.2% help, 52.0% no impact (P9C)
- Transport/roads: 44.7% help, 42.4% no impact (P9E)
- Source: Variables P9B, P9C, P9E

Participation Process Failures (P10 Series)

(SA25) Meeting Participation

- Disagreement that could participate in meetings: 417/610 = 68.4%
- Agreement that could participate: 67/610 = 11.0%
- Source: Variable P10A

(SA26) Voicing Concerns

- Disagreement that could transmit concerns: 419/610 = 68.7%
- Agreement that could voice concerns: 53/610 = 8.7%
- Source: Variable P10D

(SA27) Information Provision

- Disagreement that received sufficient information: 404/610 = 66.2%
- Agreement that received sufficient information: 69/610 = 11.3%
- Source: Variable P10E

(SA28) Developer Engagement

- Disagreement that promoter sought community involvement: 345/610 = 56.6%
- Agreement that promoter engaged community: 86/610 = 14.1%
- Source: Variable P10B

(SA29) Local Government Engagement

- Disagreement that municipality sought community involvement: 330/610 = 54.1%
- Agreement that municipality engaged community: 84/610 = 13.8%
- Source: Variable P10C

Planning Process Effects (P11 Series)

(SA30) Planning Process Effect on Solar Energy Perception

- Not affected: 322/501 = 64.3% (valid responses)
- Positively affected: 95/501 = 19.0%
- Negatively affected: 84/501 = 16.8%
- Source: Variable P11A

(SA31) Planning Process Effect on Local Park Perception

- Not affected: 322/504 = 63.9% (valid responses)
- Positively affected: 98/504 = 19.4%
- Negatively affected: 84/504 = 16.7%
- Source: Variable P11B

(SA32) Planning Process Effect on Municipal Government Confidence

- Not affected: 320/500 = 64.0% (valid responses)
- Positively affected: 109/500 = 21.8%
- Negatively affected: 71/500 = 14.2%
- Source: Variable P11C

(SA33) Planning Process Effect on Central Government Confidence

- Not affected: 342/499 = 68.5% (valid responses)
- Positively affected: 92/499 = 18.4%
- Negatively affected: 65/499 = 13.0%
- Source: Variable P11D

Future Development Priorities (P12 Series)

(SA34) Future Development Priorities

- Discuss/limit scale of parks: 75.2% agreement
- More participation opportunities: 74.9% agreement
- Greater communication: 74.3% agreement
- Individual compensatory measures: 73.8% agreement
- Municipal compensatory measures: 72.8% agreement
- Energy bill reductions: 72.6% agreement
- Mediator for interaction: 72.3% agreement
- Integration with other land uses: 71.0% agreement
- Dividends for inhabitants: 70.5% agreement
- Source: Variables P12I, P12B, P12A, P12D, P12E, P12G, P12C, P12H, P12F

Cost-Benefit Assessment (P13 Series)

(SA35) Benefits Compensate for Harms

- Agreement: 136/454 = 30.0% (valid responses)
- Most common response: Neutral (45.6%)
- Source: Variable P13A

(SA36) Harms Equal Benefits

- Agreement: 109/462 = 23.6% (valid responses)
- Most common response: Neutral (47.4%)
- Source: Variable P13B

(SA37) Harms Greater than Benefits

- Agreement: 151/465 = 32.5% (valid responses)
- Most common response: Neutral (42.4%)
- Source: Variable P13C

Land Suitability Rankings (P14 Series)

(SA38) Most Suitable Land Types for Solar Parks

- Unproductive agricultural land: 89.8% suitable

- Old waste landfills: 84.2% suitable
- Old industrial parks: 79.4% suitable
- Public (State) land: 71.8% suitable
- Around current industrial parks: 69.1% suitable
- Source: Variables P14E, P14A, P14B, P14D, P14C (combined "Adequate" + "Very Adequate")

(SA39) Least Suitable Land Types

- Productive agricultural land: 26.3% suitable
- Forest land: 43.7% suitable
- Source: Variables P14F, P14G

Alternative Land Use Preferences (P15-P17 Series)

(SA40) Alternative Land Types to Solar Parks (P15)

- Intensive olive grove adequacy: 249/536 = 46.5% adequate
- Almond grove adequacy: 247/534 = 46.3% adequate
- Hunting reserve adequacy: 203/539 = 37.7% adequate
- Source: Variables P15A, P15B, P15C (combined "Adequate" + "Very Adequate")

(SA41) Value Assessment - Intensive Olive Grove Dominance (P16)

- Economic value preference: 291/610 = 47.7% (P16A)
- Landscape integration preference: 263/610 = 43.1% (P16B)
- Conservation value preference: 260/610 = 42.6% (P16C)
- Cultural integration preference: 257/610 = 42.1% (P16D)
- Population benefits preference: 267/610 = 43.8% (P16E)
- Individual benefits preference: 263/610 = 43.1% (P16F)
- Note: Intensive olive grove ranks first across ALL value categories
- Source: Variables P16A through P16F

(SA42) Complementary Land Uses with Solar Parks (P17)

- Nature conservation adequacy: 328/533 = 61.5% adequate (P17E)
- Sheep farming adequacy: 204/522 = 39.1% adequate (P17C)
- Agriculture adequacy: 200/527 = 38.0% adequate (P17D)
- Beekeeping adequacy: 193/526 = 36.7% adequate (P17B)
- Commercial mushroom plantation adequacy: 184/506 = 36.4% adequate (P17A)
- Source: Variables P17A through P17E (combined "Adequate" + "Very Adequate")

Trust in Information Sources Complete Rankings (P18 Series)

(SA43) Highest Trust Sources

- University professors/researchers: 67.2% trust (P18A)
- Civil Protection: 63.9% trust (P18C)
- Municipality technicians: 59.8% trust (P18D)
- GNR/SEPNA: 59.7% trust (P18B)
- Local associations: 53.4% trust (P18J)
- Source: Variables P18A, P18C, P18D, P18B, P18J (combined "Trust" + "Trust Completely")

(SA44) Lowest Trust Sources

- Energy companies: 25.7% trust (P18K)
- National political decision-makers: 39.5% trust (P18F)
- Newspapers and television: 42.5% trust (P18I)
- Non-governmental organizations: 43.6% trust (P18G)

- Source: Variables P18K, P18F, P18I, P18G

Final Authorization Decision (P19)

(SA45) Final Decision Breakdown

- Would authorize: 273/610 = 44.8%
- Would not authorize: 244/610 = 40.0%
- Undecided (NS/NR): 93/610 = 15.2%
- Source: Variable P19

Additional Cross-Tabulation Analysis

(SA46) Complete Proximity-Authorization Cross-Analysis

- Daily viewers: 66/174 = 37.9% would authorize
- Occasional viewers: 154/322 = 47.8% would authorize
- Rarely see it: 43/95 = 45.3% would authorize
- Didn't know it existed: 7/13 = 53.8% would authorize
- Source: Cross-tabulation P19 × P3

(SA46) Complete Age-Authorization Cross-Analysis

- Youngest group (18-24): 28/43 = 65.1% would authorize
- Young adults (25-34): 36/62 = 58.1% would authorize
- Middle-aged (35-44): 43/77 = 55.8% would authorize
- Middle-aged (45-54): 43/89 = 48.3% would authorize
- Pre-retirement (55-64): 51/116 = 44.0% would authorize
- Older adults (65-74): 48/145 = 33.1% would authorize
- Eldest group (75+): 24/78 = 30.8% would authorize
- Source: Cross-tabulation P19 × DC3 Grupos

Annex 4 - Literature review

This section presents a targeted literature review that contextualizes the findings of this study within the broader academic and policy debate on social acceptance of renewable energy projects. It synthesizes key contributions from the literature on renewable energy siting conflicts, community perceptions, and the concept of energy justice, with particular attention to distributive, procedural, and recognition dimensions. The review also engages with recent empirical studies on solar energy deployment and local opposition dynamics, highlighting factors such as perceived local benefits, governance processes, and trust in institutions. Rather than providing an exhaustive overview, this annex focuses on the most relevant insights to interpret the results of the Portuguese case studies, offering a conceptual framework that supports the analysis presented in the main report.

Table 4.1 - This table presents the final set of 30 studies identified through a systematic literature review on perceptions and willingness to accept large solar farms in rural areas. These references represent the most relevant research drawn from an initial pool of 244 papers, which were gathered through targeted search queries, database searches using SciSpace, and citation chaining. The table summarizes the key studies that best address community perceptions, engagement, and factors influencing social acceptance of large-scale solar energy projects.

Full reference	Insights	Findings
Bessette, D.L., Hoen, B., Rand, J., Hoesch, K., White, J., Mills, S.B., Nilson, R., 2024. Good fences make good neighbors: Stakeholder perspectives on the local benefits and burdens of large-scale solar energy development in the United States. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 108, 103375. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.103375	Residents' perceptions of large-scale solar (LSS) farms in rural areas often include concerns about impacts on farmland, property values, and environmental effects. Willingness to accept LSS may decline due to insufficient information and lack of community influence over project design.	Identified concerns and strategies related to large-scale solar energy development. Examined benefits and burdens of recent LSS developments through interviews.
Biró-Varga, K., Simik, I., Stremke, S., 2024. Landscape user experiences of interspace and overhead agrivoltaics: A comparative analysis of two novel types of solar landscapes in the Netherlands. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 109, 103408. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.103408	The study indicates that while landscape users support farmers' involvement in the energy transition and the multifunctional nature of agrivoltaics, they express concerns about wildlife impacts and landscape attractiveness, reflecting mixed perceptions towards large solar farms in rural areas.	Decrease in experiential value post-agrivoltaic implementation. Increased use value for interspace, decreased for overhead systems.

Full reference	Insights	Findings
<p>Campos, I., Brito, M., Luz, G., 2023. Scales of solar energy: Exploring citizen satisfaction, interest, and values in a comparison of regions in Portugal and Spain. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 97, 102952. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.102952</p>	<p>The study indicates that social acceptance of large solar farms in rural areas varies, influenced by citizens' perceptions of the energy transition's importance and their satisfaction with participation in solar projects, highlighting the relational nature of acceptance across different installation scales.</p>	<p>Citizens' satisfaction varies with solar energy installation scale. Social acceptance relates to energy citizenship across solar production scales.</p>
<p>Carlisle, J.E., Kane, S.L., Solan, D., Bowman, M., Joe, J.C., 2015. Public attitudes regarding large-scale solar energy development in the U.S. <i>Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.</i> 48, 835–847. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.04.047</p>	<p>Respondents in rural areas are less supportive of large solar development compared to urban residents. Factors influencing acceptance include perceptions of property value impacts and scenic spoilage, with demographic variables showing mixed results in predicting support for solar farms.</p>	<p>Support for solar development varies by proximity and demographics. Environmentalism and trust in developers influence support in the Southwest.</p>
<p>Cousse, J., 2021. Still in love with solar energy? Installation size, affect, and the social acceptance of renewable energy technologies. <i>Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.</i> 145, 111107. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111107</p>	<p>The study indicates that while solar energy enjoys high socio-political acceptance, this preference diminishes for large installations, aligning more closely with attitudes towards wind energy. Affective responses significantly influence public acceptance of large solar farms in rural areas.</p>	<p>Varying degrees of landscape change observed in agrivoltaic cases. Changes in agricultural landscape pattern and openness identified.</p>
<p>Cuppari, R.I., Fernandez-Bou, A.S., Characklis, G.W., Ramirez, M., Nocco, M.A., Abou-Najm, M., 2024. Drivers of agrivoltaic perception in California and North Carolina. <i>Environ. Res. Food Syst.</i> 1, 021003. https://doi.org/10.1088/2976-601X/ad5449</p>	<p>The paper focuses on farmer perceptions of agrivoltaic systems (AVS) and their interest in installing AVS in California and North Carolina.</p>	<p>Farmers view AVS as income diversification and water reduction. Financial viability and upfront costs are major concerns.</p>
<p>Gorjian, S., Bousi, E., Özdemir, Ö.E., Trommsdorff, M., Kumar, N.M., Anand, A., Kant, K., Chopra, S.S., 2022. Progress and challenges of crop production and electricity generation in agrivoltaic systems using semi-transparent photovoltaic technology. <i>Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.</i> 158, 112126. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112126</p>	<p>The paper reviews the progress and challenges of agrivoltaic systems, specifically those using semi-transparent photovoltaic (STPV) technology for combined crop production and electricity generation.</p>	<p>While agrivoltaics offer a sustainable solution to land-use competition, there are challenges related to optimizing both crop yield and energy production</p>
<p>Hanger, S., Komendantova, N., Schinke, B., Zejli, D., Ihlal, A., Patt, A., 2016. Community acceptance of large-scale solar energy installations in developing countries: Evidence from Morocco. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 14, 80–89. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2016.01.010</p>	<p>Community acceptance of large solar farms in rural areas, particularly in Ouarzazate, Morocco, is high due to perceptions of solar power as environmentally friendly, despite low knowledge levels about the project. Concerns about unequal socio-economic benefits persist among residents.</p>	<p>Community acceptance of solar power is nearly universal. Low project knowledge correlates with high acceptance levels.</p>
<p>Hazrati, M., 2024. Social Acceptance for Renewable Energy Technologies: The Role of the Energy Justice Framework, in: Heffron, R.J., de Fontenelle, L. (Eds.), <i>The Power of Energy Justice & the Social Contract</i>. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, pp. 83–91. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-46282-5_13</p>	<p>Perceptions of large solar farms in rural areas often include concerns about property devaluation, environmental impacts, and inadequate public participation. Willingness to accept these projects can improve through trust-building, inclusive decision-making, and addressing community-specific distributive justice issues.</p>	<p>Social acceptance of renewable energy faces unexpected local resistance. Cost-effectiveness does not guarantee support for renewable energy projects.</p>

Full reference	Insights	Findings
<p>Hilker, J.M., Busse, M., Müller, K., Zscheischler, J., 2024. Photovoltaics in agricultural landscapes: “Industrial land use” or a “real compromise” between renewable energy and biodiversity? Perspectives of German nature conservation associations. <i>Energy Sustain. Soc.</i> 14, 6. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-023-00431-2</p>	<p>The study found that large-scale photovoltaic plants are locally less accepted than smaller ones, with concerns about landscape and biodiversity. There is a growing consensus for prioritizing rooftop installations and a more favorable attitude towards agrophotovoltaics over ground-mounted photovoltaics.</p>	<p>Growing consensus on need for renewable energies. Local acceptance varies for GM-PV and APV systems.</p>
<p>Ko, I., 2023. Rural opposition to landscape change from solar energy: Explaining the diffusion of setback restrictions on solar farms across South Korean counties. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 99, 103073. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.103073</p>	<p>Rural opposition to landscape change significantly influences perceptions and willingness to accept large solar farms. The study indicates that higher solar farm density correlates with increased adoption of setback restrictions, reflecting community resistance to potential landscape alterations from solar developments.</p>	<p>Rural opposition drives setback restrictions on solar farms. Higher solar farm density increases restriction adoption risk.</p>
<p>Ko, I., 2025. “Rural exploitation” in solar energy development? A field survey experiment in South Korea on solar energy support in rural areas. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 119, 103837. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103837</p>	<p>The study shows that the narratives of rural exploitation decrease support for solar energy among rural residents, particularly if they live in more remote, economically underprivileged rural areas</p>	<p>A broader historical context of rural-urban inequality should guide our understanding of the motivations and conditions of rural opposition to renewable energy development.</p>
<p>Moore, S., Graff, H., Ouellet, C., Leslie, S., Olweean, D., 2022. Can we have clean energy and grow our crops too? Solar siting on agricultural land in the United States. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 91, 102731. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102731</p>	<p>Stakeholder perceptions of large solar farms in rural areas are influenced by identity, farmland viability, and property views. Conflicts arise from differing epistemic paradigms, highlighting the need for interdisciplinary approaches to enhance acceptance and address community concerns regarding agricultural land use.</p>	<p>Stakeholder interactions shape solar siting decisions on agricultural land. Agrivoltaics may alleviate conflicts but require stakeholder engagement.</p>
<p>Nilson, R.S., Stedman, R.C., 2022. Are big and small solar separate things?: The importance of scale in public support for solar energy development in upstate New York. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 86, 102449. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102449</p>	<p>Support for utility-scale solar is significantly lower than for community or rooftop solar, with many residents perceiving it as an industrial activity that negatively impacts rural landscapes. Direct experience with utility development influences public attitudes and acceptance in rural areas.</p>	<p>Support for utility-scale solar is significantly lower than community or rooftop solar. Opposition to utility solar is common in Western New York.</p>
<p>Nilson, R.S., Stedman, R.C., 2023. Reacting to the Rural Burden: Understanding Opposition to Utility-Scale Solar Development in Upstate New York. <i>Rural Sociol.</i> 88, 578–605. https://doi.org/10.1111/ruso.12486</p>	<p>Perceptions of distributive and procedural injustice, along with place attachment, significantly influence opposition to utility-scale solar (USS) development in rural areas. The study found that 42% of residents oppose USS installations, reflecting concerns over rural burden and exploitation.</p>	<p>42% of residents oppose utility-scale solar installations. Perceived injustices and place attachment drive opposition.</p>
<p>O’Neil, S.G., 2021. Community obstacles to large scale solar: NIMBY and renewables. <i>J. Environ. Stud. Sci.</i> 11, 85–92. https://doi.org/10.1007/s13412-020-00644-3</p>	<p>The study shows that resistance to large-scale solar projects is rooted in deeper social and justice concerns rather than simple opposition to renewable energy. Local people value fairness, transparency, and control over land use, and they respond negatively when projects feel imposed or disconnected from community interests. Genuine engagement and locally shared benefits are essential for long-term acceptance of renewable energy.</p>	<p>Residents opposed large, centralized solar projects that disrupted local aesthetics and delivered few local benefits. Community-based, fairly planned, and smaller-scale solar developments gained more acceptance and trust.</p>

Full reference	Insights	Findings
<p>Pascaris, A.S., Schelly, C., Burnham, L., Pearce, J.M., 2021. Integrating solar energy with agriculture: Industry perspectives on the market, community, and socio-political dimensions of agrivoltaics. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 75, 102023. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102023</p>	<p>The paper indicates that agrivoltaics can enhance community acceptance of solar farms in rural areas by retaining agricultural interests, thus alleviating social resistance. Successful integration depends on supportive local regulations and market adoption, fostering local economic development alongside solar energy growth.</p>	<p>Agrivoltaics can enhance community acceptance of solar projects. Growth depends on market adoption and supportive regulations.</p>
<p>Pascaris, A.S., Schelly, C., Rouleau, M., Pearce, J.M., 2022. Do agrivoltaics improve public support for solar? A survey on perceptions, preferences, and priorities. <i>Green Technol. Resil. Sustain.</i> 2, 8. https://doi.org/10.1007/s44173-022-00007-x</p>	<p>The study indicates that public support for solar development increases when integrated with agricultural production, highlighting that community preferences, economic opportunities for farmers, and minimizing siting conflicts are crucial for acceptance of solar projects in rural areas.</p>	<p>81.8% support solar if integrated with agriculture. Public prefers economic benefits and local community involvement.</p>
<p>Sato, Y., Ngoc, H.B., 2024. Factors to Promote Construction of Mega-Scale Solar Power Generation Facilities from the Viewpoint of Local Residents in Vietnam. <i>Sustainability</i> 16, 10478. https://doi.org/10.3390/su162310478</p>	<p>The study indicates that local residents' perceptions and willingness to accept large solar farms are significantly influenced by comprehensive disclosures regarding construction plans, developer information, and potential economic and environmental impacts, fostering community support for mega-scale solar power generation facilities.</p>	<p>Comprehensive disclosures enhance community support for MEGA-SPG facilities. Local residents' acceptance is crucial for sustainability.</p>
<p>Schauppenlehner, T., Bittner, K., Baumgartinger-Seiringer, M., 2022. Large-Scale Agrivoltaics Visualisations for Assessing Landscape Impacts and Social Acceptance. <i>AgriVoltaics Conf. Proc.</i> 1. https://doi.org/10.52825/agripv.v1i.596</p>	<p>The research indicates that agrivoltaics may have higher acceptance due to dual land use, but significant visual impacts from large solar farms can lead to conflicts with social acceptance, necessitating effective visual assessments to facilitate discussions and decision-making.</p>	<p>Developed immersive 3D visualisations for agrivoltaics landscape impacts. Calculated indicators for economic and agricultural production influences.</p>
<p>Schwenkenbecher, A., 2017. What is Wrong with Nimbys? <i>Renewable Energy, Landscape Impacts and Incommensurable Values. Environ. Values</i> 26, 711–731. https://doi.org/10.3197/096327117X15046905490353</p>	<p>The paper argues that local opposition to renewable energy projects like wind farms is not simply selfish NIMBY behavior but often stems from genuine value conflicts, especially over landscape impacts that cannot be fairly distributed or compensated. Recognizing these protests as expressions of differing, incommensurable values can lead to more constructive responses.</p>	<p>Opposition arises less from unwillingness to share burdens and more from protecting valued landscapes. Addressing such conflicts requires ensuring procedural justice and respecting local values rather than dismissing opposition as irrational.</p>
<p>Scovell, M., McCrear, R., Walton, A., Poruschi, L., 2024. Local acceptance of solar farms: The impact of energy narratives. <i>Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.</i> 189, 114029. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.114029</p>	<p>The research indicates that general support for renewables and alignment with energy transition narratives significantly influence local acceptance of large solar farms in rural areas, while beliefs about the energy transition's broader aspects have weaker effects on acceptance.</p>	<p>Support for renewables strongly influences local solar farm acceptance. Broader energy transition narratives impact local support beyond social licence factors.</p>
<p>Sirnik, I., Oudes, D., Stremke, S., 2024. Agrivoltaics and landscape change: First evidence from built cases in the Netherlands. <i>Land Use Policy</i> 140, 107099. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2024.107099</p>	<p>The study indicates that landscape changes from agrivoltaic installations can influence social acceptance of solar power. Addressing siting and design in policy is essential to enhance acceptance of solar farms in rural areas, mitigating potential conflicts between energy and food</p>	<p>Varying degrees of landscape change observed in agrivoltaic cases. Changes in agricultural landscape pattern and openness identified.</p>

Full reference	Insights	Findings
	production.	
Stadelmann-Steffen, I., Dermont, C., 2021. Acceptance through inclusion? Political and economic participation and the acceptance of local renewable energy projects in Switzerland. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 71, 101818. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101818	The paper investigates local acceptance of renewable energy projects, finding that political and economic participation positively influences support. However, acceptance varies among individuals, indicating that perceptions of large solar farms in rural areas depend on their involvement in project processes.	Political and economic participation moderately increases support for renewable projects. Inclusion modes vary in effectiveness across different population groups.
Torma, G., Aschemann-Witzel, J., 2023. Social acceptance of dual land use approaches: Stakeholders' perceptions of the drivers and barriers confronting agrivoltaics diffusion. <i>J. Rural Stud.</i> 97, 610–625. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.01.014	The paper explores stakeholders' perceptions regarding agrivoltaics, highlighting that acceptance of large solar farms in rural areas is influenced by perceived benefits, such as economic opportunities, and barriers, including land use conflicts and environmental concerns.	Stakeholders perceive both drivers and barriers to agrivoltaics. Social acceptance influences agrivoltaics diffusion significantly.
Trandafir, S., Thomas, P., Bidwell, D., Rezendes, R., 2023. Community benefit agreements for solar energy: Examining values, preferences and perceived benefits in the United States using a discrete choice experiment. <i>Energy Res. Soc. Sci.</i> 106, 103305. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2023.103305	The study indicates that community preferences regarding large solar farms vary, with a significant disengaged majority (68.3%) and a solar-receptive group (24.2%) showing interest in private benefits, while values influence acceptance and preferences for voluntary versus mandated agreements.	Preference for private benefits over collective trust funds. Community favors voluntary implementation over government mandates.
Tsoeu-Ntokoane, S., Mosabala, T.D., Kali, M., Lemaire, X., 2024. Community imaginaries, participation and acceptance of renewable energy projects – substituting the quicksand of development with rocky fundamentals. <i>Cogent Soc. Sci.</i> 10, 2292755. https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2023.2292755	The study indicates that community acceptance of renewable energy projects, like solar farms, is significantly influenced by the level of community participation in decision-making. Higher participation correlates with greater acceptance, while minimal involvement leads to tensions and reduced sustainability.	Community participation varies from minimal to no involvement. Lower participation correlates with reduced project acceptance and sustainability.
Vuichard, P., Stauch, A., Wüstenhagen, R., 2021. Keep it local and low-key: Social acceptance of alpine solar power projects. <i>Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.</i> 138, 110516. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110516	The paper primarily focuses on alpine solar projects in Switzerland, revealing that local ownership and innovative design elements, like colored solar panels, enhance social acceptance. However, it does not specifically address perceptions of large solar farms in rural areas.	Local ownership increases social acceptance of solar projects. Colored solar panels reduce perceived landscape change.
Wagner, J., Bühner, C., Gölz, S., Trommsdorff, M., Jürkenbeck, K., 2024. Factors influencing the willingness to use agrivoltaics: A quantitative study among German farmers. <i>Appl. Energy</i> 361, 122934. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.122934	The paper indicates that 72.4% of German farmers are willing to use agrivoltaics, influenced by perceived usefulness, subjective norm, and innovativeness. However, bureaucratic efforts and regulatory uncertainties pose significant challenges to acceptance in rural areas.	72.4% of farmers are willing to use agrivoltaics. Perceived usefulness strongly influences adoption willingness.
Zander, K.K., Mathur, D., Mathew, S., Garnett, S.T., 2024. Public views about the world's largest proposed solar farm in remote Australia. <i>Energy Policy</i> 191, 114197. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2024.114197	Most respondents (70%) felt positive about the proposed solar farm, with strong support from those living nearby. However, about a third expressed concerns regarding environmental impacts, particularly Indigenous respondents, highlighting mixed	70% of respondents felt positive about the solar farm. Concerns about environmental impact, especially among Indigenous respondents.

Full reference	Insights	Findings
	perceptions and varying willingness to accept large solar farms.	

Annex 5 - Questionnaire

Disclaimer Anonimato + RGPD

Objetivo

Este inquérito integra um projeto de investigação conjunto entre a Faculdade de Ciências e o Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa.

Este projeto procura recolher opiniões das comunidades que residem perto de um parque solar de grande escala. Por parque solar referimo-nos a uma grande área de terreno com filas de painéis solares instalados no solo. Podem existir um ou vários parques solares de grande escala junto da sua área de residência.

Não existem respostas certas ou erradas, o que nos interessa é a sua opinião.

1. Contexto

De seguida irá ler um conjunto de afirmações. Por favor, indique o seu grau de concordância utilizando para tal uma escala que varia entre 1 (Discordo totalmente) e 5 (Concordo totalmente).

1.1 As alterações climáticas são um problema muito grave.

Escala:

1. Discordo totalmente
2. Discordo
3. Nem discordo nem concordo
4. Concordo
5. Concordo totalmente

1.2 O governo português faz o suficiente para combater as alterações climáticas.

Escala:

1. Discordo totalmente
2. Discordo
3. Nem discordo nem concordo
4. Concordo
5. Concordo totalmente

1.3 A transição energética (para fontes renováveis) é fundamental para combater as alterações climáticas.

Escala:

1. Discordo totalmente
2. Discordo
3. Nem discordo nem concordo
4. Concordo
5. Concordo totalmente

2. Opinião Parques Solares

2.1 Conhece o(s) parque(s) solar(es) existente(s) ou em construção perto da sua área de residência?

- Conheço bem
- Conheço-o e vejo-o todos os dias
- Conheço-o e vejo-o ocasionalmente
- Sei que existe, mas raramente o vejo
- Nem sabia que existia

2.2 Qual é a sua opinião face aos parques solares em geral?

1. Muito negativa
2. Negativa

3. Nem negativa nem positiva
4. Positiva
5. Muito positiva

2.3 Qual é a sua opinião face ao(s) parque(s) solar(es) existente(s) ou em construção perto da sua área de residência?

1. Muito negativa
2. Negativa
3. Nem negativa nem positiva
4. Positiva
5. Muito positiva

2.4 No que diz respeito ao parque solar (existente ou em construção) perto da sua área de residência, como classifica as seguintes afirmações:

- Aumenta a independência energética de Portugal
- É importante para o desenvolvimento da Região/Município
- Afeta terrenos das Reservas Ecológica ou Agrícola Nacionais
- É importante para a economia Local/Município
- Dá contrapartidas justas ao nível Local/Município
- Destroí a paisagem
- Gera conflitos com os interesses e prioridades locais
- Melhora a qualidade de vida Local/Município
- Melhora a sua qualidade de vida individual
- Ajuda a combater as alterações climáticas
- Pode tornar a energia elétrica mais barata
- Pode ter efeitos prejudiciais na flora, na fauna e no equilíbrio ecológico

Escala:

1. Discordo totalmente
2. Discordo
3. Nem discordo nem concordo
4. Concordo
5. Concordo totalmente

2.5 No que diz respeito ao(s) parque(s) solar(es) (existente(s) ou em construção) perto da sua área de residência, que impacto acha que estes(s) têm/ poderão vir a ter ao nível da:

- Criação de emprego na Região/Município
- Subida de preços de terrenos/habitação na Região/Município
- Atração de novos residentes para a Região/Município
- Atração de novos investimentos para a Região/Município
- Efeitos negativos a nível ecológico
- Melhoria das infraestruturas (e.g. estradas, transportes) e equipamentos (e.g. escolas, centros de saúde) na Região/Município
- Impactos negativos na Paisagem
- Melhoria da qualidade de vida na Região/Município
- Descida do valor da sua fatura mensal de energia

Escala:

1. Muito improvável
 2. Improvável
 3. Nem improvável nem provável
 4. Provável
 5. Muito provável
- NS

2.6 Como se sente quanto à instalação, na sua Região/Município de residência de:

- Futuros Parques Solares de grande escala
- Futuros Parques Solares de pequena escala
- Painéis Solares em Habitações e Armazéns
- Parques Eólicos de pequena escala

Escala

1. Oponho-me fortemente
2. Oponho-me
3. Nem me oponho nem apoio
4. Apoio
5. Apoio fortemente

3. Tomada de Decisão sobre Parques Solares

3.1. De forma geral, quais dos seguintes objetivos considera que deveriam ser prioridades para os líderes do seu município?

- Desenvolvimento económico
- Qualidade das escolas públicas
- Gestão do crescimento ou perda populacional
- Sustentabilidade ambiental
- Manutenção de estradas e serviços de transporte
- Fornecimento de serviços públicos (por exemplo, lixo/reciclagem)
- Ajudar a alcançar objetivos estratégicos nacionais

Assinale todos os que se aplicam

3.2 Na sua opinião, até que ponto o(s) parques solar(es) prejudicam ou ajudam estas prioridades?

- Desenvolvimento económico
- Qualidade das escolas públicas
- Gestão do crescimento ou perda populacional
- Sustentabilidade ambiental
- Manutenção de estradas e serviços de transporte
- Fornecimento de serviços públicos (por exemplo, lixo/reciclagem)
- Ajudar a alcançar objetivos estratégicos nacionais

Escala

- Prejudicam
- Não têm impacto
- Ajudam
- NS

3.3 Como classifica as seguintes afirmações sobre o planeamento do parque solar perto da sua área de residência/município?

- Pude participar em reuniões públicas sobre o processo
- O promotor do parque solar procurou ouvir e envolver a comunidade local.
- A Câmara Municipal / Junta de Freguesia procurou ouvir e envolver a comunidade local.
- Pude transmitir às autoridades as minhas preocupações sobre o parque solar antes de ser aprovado
- Foram-me dadas informações suficientes sobre o parque solar antes de ser aprovado
- O promotor do parque solar não cumpriu as promessas que fez durante o processo de planeamento
- As decisões dos responsáveis governamentais sobre o parque solar foram no melhor interesse da nossa comunidade
- O processo de planeamento associado a este parque solar foi transparente e justo

Escala:

1. Discordo totalmente
2. Discordo
3. Nem discordo nem concordo

4. Concordo
5. Concordo totalmente

3.4 Tendo em conta o processo de preparação e implementação do parque solar perto da sua área de residência:

- A minha opinião sobre a energia solar
- A minha opinião sobre este parque em particular
- A minha confiança nos técnicos e decisores políticos municipais
- A minha confiança nos técnicos e decisores políticos da administração central

Escala

- Foi afetada negativamente
- Não foi afetada
- Foi afetada positivamente

3.5 A dar-se o desenvolvimento de um novo parque solar perto da sua área de residência, que prioridades deviam ser consideradas:

- Haver maior comunicação com a população local
- Haver mais oportunidades para participação da população local no processo
- Existir um mediador que facilite a interação entre população local e promotor do parque solar
- Haver maior discussão sobre medidas compensatórias individuais
- Haver maior discussão sobre medidas compensatórias para o município
- Pagar dividendos a todos os que habitam no município do parque solar
- Garantir a integridade da paisagem e do equilíbrio ecológico
- Criar reduções na conta de energia/eletricidade de todos os que habitam no município do parque solar
- Privilegiar a integração dos painéis solares com outros usos de solo
- Discutir e até limitar a escala dos parques solares

Escala

1. Discordo totalmente
2. Discordo
3. Nem discordo nem concordo
4. Concordo
5. Concordo totalmente

3.6 Como classifica as seguintes afirmações:

- Os malefícios do Parque Solar são amplamente compensados pelos benefícios que gera
- Os malefícios do Parque Solar igualam os benefícios que gera
- Os malefícios do Parque Solar são amplamente maiores que os benefícios que gera

Escala

1. Discordo totalmente
2. Discordo
3. Nem discordo nem concordo
4. Concordo
5. Concordo totalmente

3.7 Como considera a adequação de cada tipo de terreno abaixo listado para a instalação de parques solares?

- Antigos aterros de resíduos
- Antigos parques industriais
- Em redor de atuais parques industriais
- Terrenos de propriedade pública (Estado)
- Terrenos agrícolas improdutivos
- Terrenos agrícolas produtivos
- Terrenos florestais

Escala

1. Muito desadequado

2. Desadequado
3. Nem desadequado nem adequado
4. Adequado
5. Muito adequado

3.8 Como entende cada tipo de terreno abaixo listado como alternativa preferencial ao parque solar junto à sua área de residência?

- Olival Intensivo
- Amendoal
- Reserva de Caça
- Outro: Qual?

Escala

1. Muito desadequado
2. Desadequado
3. Nem desadequado nem adequado
4. Adequado
5. Muito adequado

3.9 Que usos do solo acha adequados para complementar o terreno do parque solar junto à sua área de residência?

- Plantação Comercial de Cogumelos
- Apicultura
- Criação de Ovelhas
- Agricultura
- Conservação da natureza
- Outro, qual?

Escala

1. Muito desadequado
2. Desadequado
3. Nem desadequado nem adequado
4. Adequado
5. Muito adequado

3.10 Qual a sua confiança nas seguintes fontes de informação sobre parques solares?

- Professores / Investigadores Universitários
- GNR / SEPNA
- Proteção Civil
- Técnicos da Autarquia
- Decisores Políticos Locais
- Decisores Políticos Nacionais
- Organizações Não Governamentais
- Vizinhos
- Jornais e Televisão
- Associações Locais
- Empresas de Energia

Escala

1. Confio totalmente
2. Confio
3. Nem confio nem desconfio
4. Desconfio
5. Desconfio totalmente

3.12 Terminamos com uma pergunta aberta: Se dependesse de si teria autorizado a construção do Parque Solar junto da sua área de residência? E porquê?

4. Caracterização Geral:

- Há quantos anos vive na Região/Município/Localidade? Número
 - Conhece outros casos de parques solares fora da sua Região/Município/ Localidade? Sim Não
 - Recebeu algum pagamento associados a um parque solar? (ex. venda de terrenos) Sim Não
 - Tem ou teve algum outro benefício pessoal associado ao parque solar? Sim (qual?) Não
 - Instalou painéis fotovoltaicos na sua residência? Sim Não
 - Planeia fazê-lo? Sim Não Talvez
 - Se sim, Porquê? Aberta
 - Idade: Número
 - Género: M / F / Prefiro não dizer
 - Nível de Educação Completo: Nenhum / 4º ano / 6º ano /9º Ano / 12º Ano / Ensino Universitário / Outro – qual?
 - Atividade Atual: Empregado / Desempregado / Reformado / Outro – qual?
 - Qual das seguintes descrições se aproxima mais da situação do seu agregado familiar?
 - O rendimento atual permite viver confortavelmente
 - O rendimento atual dá para viver
 - É difícil viver com o rendimento atual
 - É muito difícil viver com o rendimento atual
-
- Se deseja receber os resultados indique email ou morada postal.

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